

Low-latitude glaciation in the Cretaceous greenhouse: reviewing the cryosphere reach during an archetypal hothouse Earth

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ABSTRACT

The traditional "Hothouse–Icehouse" dichotomy and the prevailing "Cretaceous greenhouse" narrative fail to accurately represent the geological record. Geological evidence reveals an unknown Late Cretaceous glaciation (82.8–80.96 Ma, the Campanian Barrika glaciation), with tidewater glaciers grounded at an unusually low palaeolatitude (35°N), at a time when Mesozoic temperatures have been modelled near their highest. The Barrika glaciation constitutes the last known low-latitude glaciation on Earth since the Last Paleozoic Ice Age (LPIA), which reached 30°N. The Barrika glaciation is characterized by a remarkably well-preserved glaciomarine record of subtropical tidewater glaciers associated with outlets of an extensive ice cap in Iberia. Our multiproxy analysis reveals five distinct glaciomarine units, indicative of glacial advances and retreats with a 360-kyr spacing. Calving fronts of tidewater glaciers delivered large icebergs to the palaeo-Atlantic Ocean. This glaciation correlates with a peak of ultra-depleted δD ice-sheet-related meltwater signals from Antarctica and other independent indicators of global change. This discovery of a low-latitude glaciation during a purported 'hothouse' period fundamentally challenges simplified Cretaceous climate models. It underscores the critical need for refined paleoclimate proxies and integrated Earth system modelling to fully comprehend such transient yet significant glacial episodes. The robust multiproxy workflow developed for the Barrika glaciation offers a powerful tool for identifying other unknown glaciations in deep-time greenhouse stages. Despite its generally warm reputation, the 77.06-million-year-long Cretaceous Period surprisingly records the lowest latitudinal glaciation since the Paleozoic. Remarkably, 55% of this time shows evidence of meltwaters linked to Antarctic ice sheets, with ice-rafted debris and glacial deposits present for 53% of the period. Glendonites, indicators of cold conditions, are found in 24% of Cretaceous time, and glacio-eustasy played a significant role in short-term sea-

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level changes for a striking 86% of the period. Collectively, this evidence of an active Cretaceous cryosphere is strengthened by evidence of permafrost in plateaus and high-altitude deserts, coupled by robust geochemical palaeoclimate proxies. Our findings suggest that the conventional 'hothouse-icehouse' scheme applied on deep-time climate requires reconsideration, pointing instead to a much more complex Earth climate evolution that will require a thorough re-evaluation of geochemical proxies used during the Mesozoic.

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1. Introduction and background

The Cretaceous cryosphere represents a significant, often overlooked, challenge in Mesozoic palaeoclimate modelling. In a well-known paper by [Frakes and Francis \(1988\)](#) published in *Nature* under the title “A guide to Phanerozoic cold polar climates from high-latitude ice-rafting in the Cretaceous” these forward-thinking authors stated “Indeed, there is a record of high-latitude ice-rafting throughout the Phanerozoic, suggesting that ice was present on Earth for much of its history, and that ice-free conditions could have been at most only episodic over the past 600 Myr”. Their data on ice-rafted debris (IRD) and glacial deposits during the Cretaceous have been largely omitted in palaeoclimate models and reconstructions for nearly 37 years. In fact, since 1988, the acceptance of pre-Cretaceous glacial evidence stands in contrast to the scepticism often met by Cretaceous glacial evidence among palaeoclimate modellers. This creates a paradoxical situation: since the Cretaceous is typically assumed to be a warm, ice-free period, potential signs of glaciation are often excluded from analysis of the latitudinal extent of IRD and glacial deposits ([Fig. 1](#)).

A rigorous scientific approach demands that irrefutable Cretaceous glacial evidence, if identified, prompts a re-evaluation of geochemical palaeoclimate proxies, which may have, in certain circumstances, overestimated palaeotemperatures; estimates of palaeo-pCO₂ higher than 430 ppm from stomatal indexes, for instance, should be regarded

with caution ([Barclay and Wing, 2016](#)). Deep-time glaciations have been recognized as valid for the Palaeoproterozoic and Neoproterozoic Snowball Earth condition, the Ordovician, the Carboniferous–Permian global glaciations, and the Cenozoic. By contrast, previous analysis of the latitudinal extent of these deposits led some authors to identify a distinct cryosphere gap during the Mesozoic ([Fig. 1](#)) ([Foster et al., 2017](#); [Macdonald et al., 2019](#)), omitting them also from recent palaeoclimate models of the Cretaceous world ([Scotese et al., 2025](#)).

Earth’s deep-time palaeoclimate has commonly been classified in a dualistic approach using the terms hothouse and icehouse stages (e.g., [Markwick et al., 2000](#); [Marcilly et al., 2022](#)) supplemented with blurred terms like “warmhouse”, “coolhouse”, “supergreenhouse”, “cold snaps”, and “global cooling” (e.g. [Mutterlose et al., 2009](#); [Rodríguez-López et al., 2016](#); [Westerhold et al., 2020](#); [Cavalheiro et al., 2021](#)) that have ultimately introduced confusion. This climate history (e.g., [Summerhayes, 2020](#)), however, is schematic and obscures major uncertainties about the reliability of geological evidence for the timing and duration of icehouse and greenhouse intervals, and the operation of the climate system within them. Although icehouse intervals have been inferred from generally accepted occurrences of glacial deposits in the geological record, greenhouse intervals have tended to be inferred from negative evidence of such deposits and/or positive evidence of elevated atmospheric CO₂ concentrations.

The Late Cretaceous is considered an archetypal supergreenhouse

(Huber et al., 2018) with warm temperatures at high southern palaeolatitudes (~55°S), sea-surface temperatures (SSTs) over 30°C (e.g. TEX₈₆ and δ¹⁸O-SST proxies, O'Connor et al., 2019), and high atmospheric pCO₂ levels (MacLeod et al., 2013; O'Connor et al., 2019). This palaeoclimatic evidence for a maximum hothouse of the Phanerozoic (Judd et al., 2024) conflicts with geochemical evidence of contemporaneous Antarctic ice sheets about half the size of modern ones (Bornemann et al., 2008; Nelson et al., 2022). However, identification of glaciomarine deposits from the Late Cretaceous supergreenhouse remains elusive (Huber et al., 2018). Here we report sedimentary evidence

of a newly discovered Cretaceous glaciation with a grounding line and active calving fronts releasing icebergs.

The Barrika section on the coast of the Biscay province (Basque Country, northern Spain) (Fig. 2) reveals multiproxy and multiscale evidence of this Cretaceous glaciation (Figs. 2–14, Supplementary Figs. 1–4, Supplementary Videos 1–4). We name this *the Barrika glaciation*. It occurred within a 1.84 Myr-long interval (82.8–80.96 Ma, early Campanian), covering nanofossils biozones UC14a–UC14d (Figs. 2D and 3), when an ice cap repeatedly grounded on the continental platform at a surprising low palaeolatitude (35°N) (Barrier et al., 2018; Pearce et al.,

Fig. 1. Palaeolatitudinal reach of ice-rafted debris and glaciogenic deposits from 540 Myr to Present from Foster et al. (2017) (A); Macdonald et al. (2019) (B), and in this present paper (C); note the absence of ice-rafted debris and glacial deposits during the Triassic, Jurassic and Cretaceous in previous reviews (A) and (C). The Barrika glaciation (BG) is the lowest latitudinal glaciation in the Phanerozoic since the Last Palaeozoic Ice Age (LPIA) (Jurikova et al., 2025). 1: Landing and MacGabhann (2010); 2: Retallack (2022); 3: Runkel et al. (2010); 4: Mikhailova et al. (2019); 5: Lindström (1972); 6: Macdonald et al. (2019); 7: Rosa and Isbell (2021); 8: Fielding et al. (2023); 9: Olsen et al. (2022); 10: Cather et al. (2009); 11: Schneider et al. (2020); biostratigraphy based on Zakharov et al. (1997): 12: Rodríguez-López et al. (2024); 13: Alley et al. (2020); 14: Keller and Macquaker (2015); Macquaker and Keller (2005). 16: Song et al. (2021); 17: Jeans and Platten (2021); 18: Rodríguez-López et al. (2016); 19: Gao et al. (2024); 20: Leckie et al. (1995); 21: Killops et al. (2000); 22: Tripathi and Darby (2018); 23: Birkenmajer et al. (2005); 24: Vitor and Anderson (1998); 25: Carter et al. (2017); 26: Troedson and Smellie (2002); 27: Barr et al. (2022). Geological time scale from Gradstein et al. (2020) (see Supplementary Table 1).

2022), delivering icebergs to the palaeo-Atlantic Ocean from tidewater glaciers calving fronts.

This paper presents the multiproxy analysis of the newly discovered Barrika glaciation deposits in the context of a review of multiproxy palaeoclimate analysis for the Cretaceous Period, including the latitudinal distribution of Mesozoic ice-rafted debris (IRD) and glacial deposits. A detailed Methods section is included in the accompanying Supplementary Material.

2. Geological setting

The Barrika section stands in the coast of the Biscay province (Basque Country, northern Spain) (Fig. 2A–2D) and it belongs to the geological site of interest Uribe Kosta Geosite code CB008, LIG code CV008. It is a stretch of the cliffy Basque coast located 16 km north of Bilbao city, within the Basque-Cantabrian Basin (BCB) of northern Spain (Supplementary Fig., 1A). The basin-fill evolution since Permian times records an extensional Mesozoic phase followed by a compressional Mesozoic/Cenozoic phase (Robles, 2014). The Triassic rifting phase (250–210 Ma) was followed by the Jurassic inter-rift period (210–160 Ma) and then by the Bay of Biscay rift phase spanning 160–95 Ma. The next passive continental margin development in the late Cretaceous (95–84 Ma) records lithosphere cooling, density increase and enhanced thermal subsidence, with development of flysch deposits with volcanic intercalations. The compressional phase occurred progressively from the

Santonian–Campanian boundary to the Miocene (84–15 Ma) (Carracedo et al., 2014; Robles, 2014).

The study site belongs to the municipality of Barrika, and the best outcrops occur at E–W sea-cliff exposures (Fig. 2D). Despite of the complex Alpine structural setting of the coastal outcrops (Cuevas et al., 1982), superb sedimentological sections and a high-resolution sampling and nannofossils biostratigraphy study have allowed to recognize the UC14a to UC14d nannofossils subzones in the studied section, from base to top (Figs. 2D and 3). The area is accessed from the Barrika beach parking lot and lies west of the stairs that descend to the Barrika sandy beach, along the cliffs that extend along towards *Goikomendiazpi/Atxanagusi* Point. The analysed stratigraphic interval belongs to the Barrika Formation (Fig. 2C). The latter has been traditionally referred to as “the sandy flysch” sedimentary unit reaching 1.8 km in thickness. Several stratigraphic gaps have been noted in classically interpreted deep-marine series and are indicative of the first tectonic movements of compressional closure of the BCB (Mathey, 1987). Bustillo et al. (1991) attributed a thickness of 900 m for the northern Basque Cantabrian Eibar Fm., which consists of marlstone, limestone, quartz sandy limestone, and siltstone. This unit, and in particular at the Barrika section, lacks previous detailed sedimentological studies, and were generally ascribed to deep marine slumps, olistostromes and turbidites deposited under the catch-all term “flysch” (Mathey, 1987; Elorza and Bustillo, 1989), which is a term commonly used referring to Mesozoic to Cenozoic marine deposits in the Basque Coast. We present multi-proxy evidence of the

Fig. 2. Geological Setting. (A), and (B), Geological maps of Iberia and the Basque-Cantabrian Basin (BCB) and location of the study area (after Fernández-Mendiola et al., 2023). (C) Chronostratigraphical chart and location of the Barrika Fm. (D) Panoramic view of the Barrika Section in the Basque coast (Barrika-Sopela localities) in the geological site of interest Uribe Kosta Geosite. The stratigraphic locations of the nannofossil subzones of biozone UC14 are indicated as well as the sedimentary record of the Campanian Barrika glaciation. See detailed sedimentological sections and palaeogeographic map in Supplementary Fig. 1.

glaciomarine and subglacial facies associations provided in Figs. 1–14, Supplementary Figures 1–4, Supplementary Videos 1–4, and Supplementary Tables 1–4.

3. Barrika glaciation phytoplankton analysis

3.1. Diversity of assemblages

A total of 91 taxa of calcareous nannofossils were identified in the Barrika succession (Fig. 3, Supplementary Table 2). The overall diversity (number of taxa) is high in all studied samples. Analysis of the calcareous nannofossil data indicates that the assemblages are dominated by

genus *Watznaueria* ssp. (24.8%) (Fig. 4A [17]), *Eiffellithus* ssp. (7.2%) (Fig. 4A [1–5]), *Biscutum* ssp. (6.1%) (Fig. 4A [20]), *Prediscosphaera* ssp. (5.2%) (Fig. 4A [7–10]), *Micula* ssp. (4.1%) (Fig. 4B [17–21]) and *Retecapsa* ssp. (3.6%) (Fig. 4A [13]), as well as by the species *Tranolithus orionatus* (9.2%) (Fig. 4A [15–16]), *Cribrosphaerella ehrenbergii* (5.5%) (Fig. 4A [11–12]) and *Reinhardtites anthophorus* (3.8%) (Fig. 5A [20a–21]). The other species have low or very low average abundances (R: rare abundance). The *Aspidolithus parvus* lineage (Fig. 4A [23–28]), with high biostratigraphic significance, is characterized by a rare and sporadic abundance, although *Aspidolithus parvus parvus* (Fig. 4A [24–26]) is less uncommon than the other subspecies, *Aspidolithus parvus expansus* (Fig. 4A [23]) and *Aspidolithus parvus constrictus* (Fig. 4A

Fig. 3. Glaciomarine record of the 1.84 Myr Barrika glaciation (early Campanian, 82.8–80.96 Ma). Multiproxy analysis of the restored-composite section of the Barrika section show the temporal distribution of five glaciomarine units (1 to 5 from base to top) and their nannofossils biostratigraphy (successive subzones UC14a to UC14d). Glacial features (including ice-rafted striated dropstones, striated bullet shaped clasts in diamicrites facies and diamicrites in the glaciomarine units) correlate with increases in glacially multistriated ice-rafted biodebris (IRDb) (confirmed by SEM) and cool-water/high-latitude nannofossil taxa (Fig. 5A). Ninety-nine records of cool-water and high-latitude nannofossil taxa, together with occurrence of IRDb, both during deposition of the five glaciomarine units and the interbedded intervals of distal marine facies, demonstrate that glacial conditions sustained at 35°N of palaeolatitude during the entire nannofossil biozone UC14. See detailed percentages of taxa in Supplementary Table 2, and the stratigraphic sections and legend in Supplementary Figs. 1B–1F

Fig. 4. Micrographs of calcareous nannofossils from the Barrika section. (A) and (B), Cross-polarized light micrographs taken at 1250 x magnification. Lower-right numbering refers to sample number, and (Xa) and (Yb) refer to simple polarized light and gypsum plate, respectively. In (B) Photographs 32 to 35 are reworked Cenomanian specimens.

[27a–28]). Other stratigraphically-relevant taxa, such as *Bukryaster hayi* (Fig. 4B [26a–27b]), *Ceratolithoides verbeekii* (Fig. 4B [28a–29b]), *Marthasterites furcatus* (Fig. 4B [25]) or *Reinhardtites cf. levis* (Fig. 4B [12a–14]), are extremely rare in the studied samples.

3.2. Biostratigraphy

The nannofossil biozonations adopted are those proposed by Sissingh (1977) and modified by Perch-Nielsen (1985) (CC) and that of Burnett

(1998) (UC: TP tethyan). Traditionally, the lowest occurrence of *A. parvus parvus* was considered as a marker for the Santonian–Campanian boundary (Gale et al., 1995; Gale et al., 2008), although its appearance is known to be diachronous. Recent work on the *Aspidolithus parvus* lineage (Miniati et al., 2020) established a succession of subspecies through the latest Santonian and early Campanian. The lowest occurrence of *A. parvus parvus*, used to define the base of the biozones CC18 (Sissingh, 1977; Perch-Nielsen, 1985) and UC14 (Burnett, 1998), now has been situated below the boundary Santonian–Campanian

Fig. 5. Cool-water, high-latitude nannofossils and principal components of the Barrika glaciation. (A) Cool-water and high-latitude calcareous nannofossils taxa. Cross-polarized light micrographs of high-latitude taxa (1a–b, *Ahmullerella octoradiata*; 10–11, *Gartnerago constatum*; 12–14, *Gartnerago segmentatum*; 15a–16, *Kamptnerius magnificus*) and cool-water species (2a–4, *Arkhangelskiella cymbiformis*; 5a–9, *Eprolithus floralis*; 17–19, *Crisbrosphaerella ehrenbergii*; 20a–21, *Reinhardtites anthophorus* and 22–24, *Tranolithus orionatus*) from Barrika section. Scale bar is 5 μ m. Lower code (BAR-) refers to sample number, and (Xa) and (Yb) refer to simple polarized light and gypsum plate, respectively. (B) and (C) display the loads and scores, respectively, from the PCA applied to all data (ice-rafted debris, reworked Cenomanian taxa, and nannofossil assemblages). (D, E and F) display the loads (D) and scores (E, coloured by diamiccite vs. non-diamictite, and (F) coloured by relative stratigraphic position) for the nannofossil-only PCA results.

(Miniati et al., 2020; Gale et al., 2023). Other bioevents of *Aspidolithus parvus* lineage, such as the consistent record of *A. parvus parvus* and the first occurrence of *A. parvus constrictus*, provide a useful and consistent marker of the Lower Campanian (Fig. 3, Supplementary Table 2).

In the Barrika section, all the samples between BAR-15B and BAR-138 contain *A. parvus parvus*; hence they are assigned to subzones CC18a of Sissingh (1977) and Perch-Nielsen (1985) and UC14a of Burnett (1998). The first occurrence of *A. parvus constrictus* was identified in

(caption on next page)

Fig. 6. FEGSEM (A–F and H–P), and micro-CT and nano-CT Synchrotron (G) images of ice-rafted debris (IRD) from distal glaciomarine marlstones facies of the Barrika glaciation that also contains cool-water / high-latitude nannofossils, ice-rafted biodebris (IRDb), and ice-rafted dropstones (IRDp). (A) Angular and abraded IRD 300 μm showing an elongated and deep groove. (B) Faceted IRD of 350 μm showing parallel deep grooves. (C) Detail from (B) showing parallel grooves and abraded ridges. (D) IRD of 300 μm showing faceted edges and deep curved scars. (E) Close up view of an IRD showing a striated groove. (F) Detail from (E) showing the striated grooved due to the subglacial ploughing of a clast on the IRD surface. (G) Micro-CT and Nano-CT Synchrotron images of IRD containing glacial striations preserved by covering sedimentary particles. Red arrow indicates the location of the nano-CT scan point analysis. Successive (1–5) rotational 3D nano-scale rendering shows the scanned point showing the striated quartz surface of the IRD (brown semi-transparent colour), the glacial striations on the surface and the striation casts on the basal part of the sedimentary particle (white colour). White arrows point out the location of the glacial striations on the IRD surface (Supplementary Video 1). (H) IRD of 450 μm showing abraded and angular edges. (I) Detail from (H) showing three sets of glacial cross-cutting striation sets. (J) IRD of 300 μm showing angular and abraded edges. (K) Close up view from IRD in (J) showing conchoidal fractures on the surface. These conchoidal fractures contains parallel striations on the surface as seen in (L). (M) IRD surface showing a glacially abraded surface containing several families of crescentic scars (lunate fractures), crescentic gouges and striations. (N) Detail from (M) showing trains of crescentic scars and gouges together with striated polished surfaces. (O) Close up view from (M) showing cross-cutting striation families (3) consistent with the orientation of families of crescentic scars (lunate fractures) (1) and crescentic gouges (2). (P) Striations on the surface of an IRD grain.

sample BAR-130 and marks the base of UC14b subzone of Burnett (1998), in such a way that samples of the interval between BAR-130 and BAR-127 are included in UC14b subzone of Burnett (1998) (Fig. 3). The stratigraphic interval represented by samples BAR-128 to BAR-2 can be assigned to subzones undifferentiated CC18b/c of Sissingh (1977) and Perch-Nielsen (1985) and UC14c/d of Burnett (1998), due to the coexistence of *B. hayi*, *C. verbeekii* and the presence of *Eprolithus floralis* (Fig. 3) and *M. furcatus*. In addition, these samples record the first occurrence of *R. cf. levis*, although this bioevent must always be considered with caution due to presence of intermediate forms between this species and *R. anthophorus*, and the overgrowth of coccoliths in poorly preserved samples (Razmjooei et al., 2018; Razmjooei et al., 2020a). Reworked specimens of *Prediscosphaera columnata* (Fig. 4B [32]), *Corollithion kennedyi* (Fig. 4B [33]), *Rhagodiscus achlyostaurion* (Fig. 4B [34]), *Cretarhabdus striatus* (Fig. 4B [35]) were found in some samples of the Barrika section (Fig. 3, and Supplementary Table 2). Evidence of reworking is also provided by the occurrence of recrystallized and broken specimens (Fig. 4B [30,31,35]). The presence of Cenomanian-restricted species, as *C. kennedyi*, suggests reworking of Cenomanian sediments within samples of the Barrika section. Cenomanian-restricted species were found in Campanian sediments from Site 877 on Wodejebato Guyot by Erba et al. (1995). The vertical distribution of biostratigraphic index taxa together with biozones identified is summarized in Supplementary Table 2.

According to the distribution of calcareous nannofossil biostratigraphic markers, the sediments of the Barrika section spans subzones CC18a to CC18b/c of Sissingh (1977) and Perch-Nielsen (1985) and UC14a to UC14c/d of Burnett (1998). Therefore, the stratigraphic interval of the Barrika section is attributed to the early Campanian, corresponding to an absolute age of 82.8 to 80.96 Ma (Gale et al., 2020) (Fig. 2 and 3).

3.3. Palaeotemperature

Several calcareous nannofossil species are recognized as cool-water indicators. A southward migration of high-latitude taxa and an increase of the cool-water species are associated with a cooler climate (Voigt et al., 2004; Linnert et al., 2014; Linnert et al., 2018). The presence, in a significant (but low) proportion, of *Ahmuellerella octoradiata* (Fig. 5A [1a–b]), *Gartnerago spp.*, (Fig. 5A [10–14]) *Kamptnerius magnificus* (Fig. 5A [15a–16]), considered as high-latitude taxa (Thibault and Gardin, 2006, 2010; Linnert et al., 2011; Thibault et al., 2016), and *Arkhangelskiella cymbiformis* (Fig. 5A [2a–4]), collectively indicate a generalized cool surface water environment in the Barrika succession. In addition, the increase in abundance of *Eprolithus floralis* (sample BAR-23B) (Fig. 5A [5a–9]), *Tranolithus orionatus* (Fig. 5A [22–24]), *Cribsphaerella ehrenbergii* (Fig. 5A [17–19]) and *Reinhardtites anthophorus* (Fig. 5A [20a–20b]), often considered a cool-water species (Lees, 2002; Bornemann et al., 2005; Watkins and Self-Trail, 2005; Hardas and Mutterlose, 2007; Linnert et al., 2010; Linnert et al., 2011) and the very low abundance/absence of genus *Rhagodiscus*, together with the low relative abundance of the cosmopolitan taxon *W. barnesae* (26.29%),

both interpreted as indicators of warm waters (Thibault and Gardin, 2007; Razmjooei et al., 2020b), also suggest cool surface water conditions during this interval. Although the results should be considered with caution, since a quantitative study of the calcareous nannofossil associations was not carried out, the presence and relative abundance of these taxa suggest cold-water conditions for the lower Campanian in the Barrika section.

3.4. Principal components analysis

Principal components analysis (PCA) on the occurrence of IRD, reworked Cenomanian fossils, and nannofossil abundance data from the glaciomarine deposits helped to characterize their relationship with each other. Two PCAs were run, one with all three datasets and one with only nannofossil data (Fig. 5B–5F).

The “all data PCA” results in two statistically significant principal components: PC1 (32.0% of variance) is positively correlated with higher proportions of IRD and reworked Cenomanian fossils in the sediments, whereas PC2 (14.7% of variance) is positively correlated with the proportion of IRD and anti-correlated with reworked Cenomanian fossil occurrences. No particular nannofossils or nannofossil assemblages are significantly correlated or anti-correlated with either PC, and no cool-water nannofossil taxa are highly correlated with the occurrence of IRD or reworked Cenomanian taxa (Fig. 5B–5F). Thick diamicrite intervals have consistently positive PC1 and/or PC2 scores and are statistically distinct from the intervening marlstone intervals that have consistently negative PC1 and PC2 scores. Cool-water nannofossils prevailed throughout the 1.84 Myr duration of deposition (Fig. 5B–5F)—i.e., both during glacial maxima characterized by thick subglacial diamicrites and proglacial diamicrites with ice-rafted debris (IRD), ice-rafted dropstones (IRDp), and ice-rafted biodebris (IRDb) and glacial minima (marlstones and varved mixed carbonates and sandstones with IRD, IRDp and IRDb). Maxima of IRDb and reworked Cenomanian fossils occurred during glacial maxima and were also detected in the marlstone intervals (Fig. 5B–5F).

The “nannofossil-only” PCA resulted in only a single statistically significant PC above random (PC1; 18.8% of variance); PC2 accounted for 12.4% of the variance. Sample scores plotted for this PCA show that PC1 does not correlate with glacial maxima (diamicrites) vs. minima (marlstones) but rather tracks stratigraphic changes in the extant fossil assemblage up-section. For example, the base of the section contains more abundant cool-water taxa such as *Reinhardtites anthophorus* and *Kamptnerius magnificus*, and non-cool-water taxa such as *Calculites ovalis* and *Tetrapodorhabdus decorus*; the upper part of the section shows different extant cool-water taxa (*Tranolithus orionatus*) and non-cool-water taxa (*Prediscosphaera spinosa*, *Chiastozygus litterarius*) (Fig. 5B–5F).

4. Glacial sedimentology of the Barrika glaciation

The Campanian Barrika glaciation occurred within 1.84 Myr-long interval, spanning nannofossil biozones UC14a to UC14d. During these 1.84 Myr (Fig. 3), five decametric to metre-thick glaciogenic units

Fig. 7. (A) Drill cores and core casts obtained from distal glaciomarine marlstones with rounded and abraded floating ice-rafted debris (IRD) (marked with white arrows) (lithofacies [Fm(d)] and [Fl(d)]). This lithofacies formed in distal glaciomarine settings were icebergs released by melting IRDp, IRD and pre-Campanian ice-rafted biodebris (IRDb). These glaciomarine marlstones also contain cool-water and high-latitude nannofossils taxa. (B–D) Ice-rafted biodebris (IRDb) from the Campanian Barrika glaciation. (B) Thickness maps from a 3D mesh model (on chambers sediment and tests); and (C) on test only, obtained by synchrotron X-ray micro-computed tomography of a multistriated IRDb (*Globotruncana linneiana*) (see Supplementary Video 2). (D) Close-up view showing four crosscutting glacial striation sets on the IRDb surface. (E) Scanning electron micrograph of multistriated IRDb (*Sigalia carpatica*) obtained from Campanian glaciomarine marlstones with ice-rafted dropstones (A). Colour lines indicate cross-cutting striation directions. (F) Close-up view showing the zig-zag pattern of glacial multistriations, including arc-shaped striations (curved white arrow). Lines indicate five glacial striation sets. (G) Ice-rafted biodebris (IRDb) planktic foraminiferal specimens from glaciomarine units and marlstones in between glaciomarine units showing polished and microstriated surfaces. 1. *Globotruncana linneiana* (sample BAR-93); 2. *Dicarinella asymetrica* (sample BAR-70); 3. *Marginotruncana coronata* (sample BAR-54); 4. *Sigalia carpatica* (sample BAR-93); 5. *Heterohelix sphenoides* (sample BAR-15B). SEM photographs of specimens from inside the diamictites, showing partially polished surfaces with microstriae: 6. *Marginotruncana pseudolinneiana* (BAR-26B); 7. *Marginotruncana sinuosa* (sample BAR-26B); 8. *Thalmaninella brotzeni* (BAR-23B); 9. *Whiteinella aprica* (BAR-23B); 10. *Praeglobotruncana gibba* (BAR-26B); 11a and 11b. *Contusotruncana fornicata* (BAR-26B). Scale-bar = 100 μm . See sample's location on Fig. 3.

Fig. 8. (A–H), Distal glaciomarine lithofacies showing laminated marine marlstones containing faceted and multistriated ice-rafted dropstones (IRDp) and ice-rafted debris (IRD) (see Figs. 6 and 7A) delivered by drifting icebergs. Note the impact structures formed as dropstones hit the ocean floor, and the draping lamination covering IRDp. The faceted, multi-striated surfaces of the glacial dropstones indicate prior subglacial transport. These mudstones with IRDp, IRD and IRDb contain cool-water and high-latitude nannofossils. (I) and (J) are rock polished slides showing the IRDp and IRD floating in proglacial marlstones that contain cool water and high-latitude nannofossils and IRDb (Fig. 7B–7D).

(Glaciomarine Units 1 to 5) are interbedded with distal marine lithofacies mixed carbonate varved intervals and interbedded laminated marlstones that also contain ice-rafted dropstones (IRDp), ice-rafted debris (IRD) and ice-rafted biodebris (IRDb) (Figs. 2D and 3). We present multi-proxy evidence of the glaciomarine and subglacial facies associations provided in Figs 1–15, Supplementary Figs. 1–4, Supplementary Videos 1–4, and Supplementary Tables 2–4 that allow to establish a three-fold proximal-to-distal spatial pattern of glacial and proglacial subenvironments (Fig. 15B and 15C) as those described from

other well-known ancient and modern glaciomarine systems (e.g., Powell, 1981, 1984; Visser, 1997; Smith and Andrews, 2000; Marcos et al., 2018; Domack and Powell, 2018; Dowdeswell et al., 2019).

4.1. Ice-rafted debris (IRD)

Ice-rafted debris (IRD) appears as coarse sand- to granule-size (0.5 to 3 mm) grains suspended within the 4 μm mean size of the host marlstones (e.g., McKay et al., 2022) (Figs. 6A–6P and 7A) together with cool

Fig. 9. (A–F) Ice-rafted dropstones (IRDp) from drifting icebergs in outer proximal glaciomarine environments. IRDp are faceted, shows abraded edges and striations on the surfaces. Inherited diagenetic calcites contained on the IRDp. (C) U-Pb geochronological ages and isochron plots of two calcite veins from ice-rafted dropstones (D) dating them as Jurassic and Albian (Supplementary Fig. 4 and Supplementary Table 3). Note the dramatic impact structures of the IRDp leading to deformation of glaciomarine marlstones with IRD. Long axis of the IRDp in (E and F) is oriented perpendicular to the stratification. Glaciomarine turbidites from the grounding zone wedge (GZW) are draping the protruding top of the IRDp; note that before the glacioturbidites covered them, the proglacial marlstones already started to drape to margins of the IRDp.

and high-latitude nannofossils assemblages (Figs. 3 and 5). IRD comprises angular to subangular grains that show associations of microscopic surface structures, at both Field Emission Gun–Scanning Electron Microscope (FEG-SEM) (Fig. 6A–F and 6H–6P) and Micro-CT and Nano-CT Synchrotron scale (Fig. 6G, Supplementary Video 1), commonly observed in recent and ancient glacially, crushed mineral clasts that underwent intense subglacial transport (e.g., Mahaney, 2002; Gao et al.,

2012), abrasion by meltwaters (e.g., Mahaney and Kalm, 2000) and glacial plucking (e.g., Passchier et al., 2021).

The microstructures on angular and subangular IRD from the Campanian of Iberia include: (i) faceted, polished and abraded surfaces on grain edges (Fig. 6A, 6B and 6D) (cf., Van Hoesen and Orndorff, 2004); (ii) conchoidal fractures (Fig. 6K and 6L) (cf., Mahaney et al., 2001; Mahaney, 2002; Van Hoesen and Orndorff, 2004); (iii) striated surfaces

Fig. 10. (A–C) Rainout glacial diamicrites with interbedded IRD and IRDp intervals [Dmm(d)-Dml(d)-Fl-Fm] (see Supplementary Table 4) show alternating iceberg activity and marine sedimentation. IRDp and IRD impact structures indicate forceful ocean floor impacts, with IRDp diverting lamination by 53° and reducing its thickness. Draping lamination covers faceted IRDp; dropstones’ long axes are perpendicular to stratification (S₀). (D–F) Undermelt glacial diamicrites [Dmm(d)-Dms (d)] (Supplementary Table 4) (see Supplementary Video 4) formed from till clasts dropped from ice shelves of tidewater glaciers, contain bullet-shaped IRDp with impact structures, puncturing, and downturned lamination (E and F). Dropstones long axes are vertical to depositional surface (S₀), covered by draping diamicrite lamination.

Fig. 11. Subglacial traction tillites [Dms(d)(s)], comprising sheared, stratified diamictites with dropstones, formed through subglacial deformation of proglacial undermelt diamictites [Dms(d)] containing dropstones when overridden by an advancing grounding line (Supplementary Table 4). (A) Subglacial traction tillite contains clast pavements formed by faceted and multistriated ploughed clasts. Clasts are varied in lithology including Albian volcanics (1), dark grey (2) and pale beige (3) Cretaceous limestones. (B–D) Faceted and multistriated ploughed clast (1 in A). (D–E) Subglacial traction tillite matrix contains other ploughed clasts (1), pressure shadows (2), grain stacks (3), and rotational (galaxies) structures (4). (F) Subglacial faceted and multistriated ploughed clast (2 in A), showing evidence of ice-till interactions with two cross-cutting sets of glacial striations. Subglacial ploughing of a keeled volcanic clast on the striated surface of the limestone clast formed two deep grooves parallel to striation sets 1. (G) SEM image from (F) showing the ploughing clast and the deep curved grooves associated with the clast's keel, as well as the two cross-cutting striation sets. (H) Close up view of the subglacial ploughed clast (3 in A) which shows a stoss-lee faceted geometry and an abraded upper surface. (I) This diamictite clast is associated with a tillite microfabric showing a carapace of clasts in front of the ploughed clast, other heterolithic ploughed clasts (1), turbate structures (2), pressure shadows (3), and rotational structures (4), all of them evidence of subglacial traction tillites.

Fig. 12. Glacial undermelt diamictite with ice-rafted dropstones, sheared by overridden subglacial ice. (A) Stratified diamictites with ice-rafted dropstones affected by subsequent subglacial shear (subglacial traction tillite) [Dms(d)(s)] (Supplementary Table 4). (B) Detail showing the dramatic impact structure of the IRDp. This IRDp is covered by lamination of the stratified diamictites. (C) Note the erosion (deformation/dispersion) tail formed in the diamictite (subglacial traction tillite) evidence of ice-soft sediment contact.

with cross-cutting multistriation sets (Fig. 6E–6G, 6I, 6L, 6P and Supplementary Video 1) (cf. Hoffman and Schrag, 2002; Rodríguez-López et al., 2024); (iv) deep striated parallel grooves bounded by abraded edges (Fig. 6A–6C) (Mahaney and Kalm, 2000); (v) grooves with parallel striations and associated ploughed clasts (Fig. 6E and 6F) (e.g., Rodríguez-López et al., 2024); and (vi) chattermarks, including crescentic gouges and associated lunate fractures (Fig. 6M–6O) (cf., Gao et al., 2012; Le Heron et al., 2020b). Crescentic gouges from the IRD of the Barrika glaciation resemble those described from IRD of Pliocene glaciations and formed by the combined action of persistent overburden pressure and sliding of subglacial sole glacier ice fracturing and gouging by rock fragments (Gao et al., 2012). These are coherent with the directions observed of coeval glacial striations on the IRD (Fig. 6M–6O). Collectively, these glacial-erosion features preserved in IRD surfaces

from glaciomarine facies of the Barrika glaciation are similar to IRD previously reported from ancient and recent glaciomarine settings. Regarding ancient environments, the IRD of the Barrika glaciation show similarities with the glacial diamictites of the Proterozoic of Brazil (Araújo and Nogueira, 2019) and the early Cretaceous of Australia (Alley and Frakes, 2003), the glaciomarine diamictites of the Paleozoic of China (An et al., 2023), the glaciolacustrine deposits in the Cretaceous of Spain (Rodríguez-López et al., 2024), and the glacial deposits associated with ice sheets in the Pliocene of Canada (Gao et al., 2012). Recent counterparts include the proglacial sediments from the Russell Glacier in Greenland (Kalińska-Nartiša et al., 2017), the diamictites (Shrivastava et al., 2014) and glacial sediments in Antarctica (Warrier et al., 2016), the glacial Quaternary sediments in SW USA (Van Hoesen and Orndorff, 2004), the Late Pleistocene ocean sediments from the triple junction of the South Atlantic, South Indian, and Southern oceans (Marino et al., 2013) due to Antarctic iceberg melt (Starr et al., 2021), the Northwest Pacific IRD linked with late Quaternary ice-sheets in northeast Siberia (McCarron et al., 2021), and the debris-rich basal ice layers of the NEEM ice core (NW Greenland) (Blard et al., 2023). They all show fractality, bearing glacial erosion features like those observed in meter- to km-scale subglacial abraded surfaces (cf., Krabbendam et al., 2017; Dietrich et al., 2021).

4.2. Ice-rafted biodebris (IRDb)

4.2.1. IRDb in the Campanian Barrika glaciation

IRDb consists of multistriated reworked pre-Campanian foraminifera tests (0.4–0.7 mm) within glaciomarine marlstones (averaging 4 μm in size), containing IRD and IRDp, cool-water and high-latitude nanofossils, and showing horizontal undeformed and continuous and undisturbed faint lamination (Fig. 7A–7E, Supplementary Figs. 2–3 and Supplementary Video 2). The occurrence of IRDb in association with IRD and IRDp (Fig. 7A–7G) is widespread during the whole duration of the Barrika glaciation (biozones UC14a to UC14d), including glaciation maxima and minima (Fig. 3). Analysis of planktic foraminifera on the European Synchrotron (Supplementary Video 2) together with scanning electron microscopy (SEM) demonstrates the occurrence of more than 4 cross-cutting striation sets affecting only one of the sides of the IRDb (Figs. 7B–7F and Supplementary Fig. 3) with an intact preservation of the sedimentary infill and chamber structures (Supplementary Video 2). The same pattern of cross-cutting glacial striations observed in IRDb (Supplementary Videos 2), is also evident on (i) IRD (Supplementary Video 1), IRDp (Figs. 8, 9 and 11); (ii) meter-scale glacial rafts (Fig. 14F and 14G), and (iii) on multistriated subglacial clasts (Fig. 13A–13I) and Supplementary Video 3).

Planktic foraminifera are very scarce in the 23 samples collected outside the diamictites in the Barrika section (Figs. 3 and 7G, Supplementary Figs. 2–3). The specimen number per 250 g of washed sample in glacial minima intervals varies between 0 and 136, with an average of 41 specimens and contrasts with the > 2,000 specimens found in all the marly samples collected within the glaciomarine units (1–5) (Figs. 3, Supplementary Figs. 2–3). Across the complete section, preservation of planktic foraminiferal tests varies from very poor to moderate, even within the same sample. Several mechanisms of taphonomic alteration of the tests were identified, including dissolution, fragmentation, abrasion (which produced polished and microstriated surfaces), and sedimentary infillings of chambers (e.g., micrite, glauconite or pyrite).

The stratigraphic distributions of 44 planktic foraminiferal species from the Barrika section span the uppermost Albian to Santonian interval (Supplementary Fig. 2). Foraminifera occur as reworked IRDb in early Campanian marlstones dated using detailed nanofossil biostratigraphy (Fig. 3 and Supplementary Table 2). Reworking of foraminifera tests is also suggested by: (i) species of *Dicarinella*, *Muricohedbergella*, *Planomalina*, *Praeglobotruncana*, *Pseudothammanninella*, *Rotalipora*, *Sigalia*, *Thalmaninella*, *Whiteinella* and most species of *Marginotruncana*, listed in Supplementary Fig. 2, already extinct in the early Campanian,

Fig. 13. (A) Glacial multistriated bullet-shaped clast. (B) Micro computed tomography (micro-CT) scan of the striated glacial clast (Supplementary Video 3). (C) Close-up view from (A) shows multi-directional glacial striations, including curved striations. Arrows point out micro-chatter marks showing multiple ice displacement directions concordant with striations directions. (D–E) Subglacial clast showing cross-cutting striation sets. (F) Subglacial ploughed clast formed by a rounded sandstone clast deeply ploughed into a limestone subglacial clast both forming part of a subglacial diamictite with dropstones. (G) Subglacial clast showing a deep striated groove with diamictite matrix postdating the striations. (H) Subglacial clast showing facets and cross-cutting striations sets which are postdated by the glacial diamictite matrix. (I) Bullet-shaped striated subglacial clast. It shows a snout (pointing up glacier) and a heavily fractured side (pointing down glacier); radial pattern of glacial striations on its surface coherent with the ice displacement direction.

Fig. 14. Tidewater glacier grounding line with subglacial rafts in the Barrika glaciation. (A) Prow and groove structures on subglacial raft upper surfaces provides evidence of subglacial clast lodgment and clast ploughing due to basal glacier ice sliding. (B) Glacial raft upper surface showing ploughed clasts and associated frontal prows and parallel grooves and striations. (C) Aerial photograph of glaciomarine unit 5 (Fig. 2) showing a large (>4 m high) glacial raft. Its base is encased on a glacially abraded substrate; the sustained subglacial dragging and ploughing led to lateral paraxial ridges with a lateral banded margin (1) and an abraded margin (2). Subglacial diamictites with ice-rafted dropstones and striated bullet-shaped clasts are onlapping the large glacial raft (3). The base of the glacial raft show grooves and striations (4). (D) Close up view from (C) showing the glacial raft striated base and the lateral ridge (1 in C). (E) Detail of the onlapping of subglacial diamictites on the abraded margin of the glacial raft. Note the intense abrasion on the margin (2 in C) due to the subglacial dragging of the raft on the substrate. Stratigraphic top to the lower left corner. (F) Close up view to the glacial raft base showing well-developed striations (4, in C). (G) Detail of a multistriated and abraded bullet-shaped subglacial clast (3 in C) encased on diamictites onlapping the glacial raft.

Fig. 15. (A) Recent analogue of the Barrika glaciation icebergs, showing a flipped over iceberg drifting offshore of the northern Antarctic Peninsula exposing basal till clasts, including boulders ~3m long (white arrow). (B) Reconstructed glaciomarine dynamics of the Barrika glaciation. Red colours refer to figure labels (Modified and adapted from Smith et al., 2019; under CC by 4.0 <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/deed.es>).

according to the biostratigraphic ranges proposed by Premoli Silva and Sliter (1995), and Coccioni and Premoli Silva (2015); and (ii) planktic foraminiferal assemblages often exhibit the same and consistent mixture of individuals from similar ages, especially, but not only, within all the glaciomarine units (glacial diamictites matrices). The species found at Barrika range in age from the uppermost Albian (e.g., *P. buxtoni* and probably *T. appenninica* and *P. bentonensis*), Cenomanian (e.g., species of *Praeglobotruncana*, *Pseudothalmaninella*, and *Rotalipora*, as well as *T. brotzeni* and *T. greenhornensis*) and the uppermost Coniacian–Santonian (including most of the identified species of *Conusotruncana*, *Costellagerina*, *Dicarinella*, *Globotruncana*, *Marginotruncana*, *Pseudotextularia*, and *Sigalia*). Reworking is also consistent with the occurrence of reworked Cenomanian nannofossils in the diamictites from the glaciomarine units (32–35 in Fig. 4B); (iii) scarcity or total absence of planktic foraminifera outside the diamictites (Supplementary Fig. 2); and (iv) coexistence of multiple mechanisms of taphonomic alteration and variable degree of preservation of the tests, even in the same sample.

Of the 105 specimens with well-preserved tests selected for SEM, more than 43% have surfaces with signs of polishing and microstriation (Fig. 7B–7G). This suggests that the glacial striae are much more common among the most poorly preserved specimens. Planktic foraminiferal specimens with polished and microstriated surfaces are frequent both in the stratigraphic intervals interbedded with glaciomarine units (1–5 in Fig. 7G) and within the glaciomarine units (6–11 in Fig. 7G); this fact, together with the occurrence of cool-water/high-latitude nannofossil taxa, IRDp and IRD in the same samples, provides evidence of drifting icebergs during both glacial maxima and minima (Fig. 3) during the time span of the Barrika glaciation (82.8 to 80.96 Ma).

4.2.2. IRDb in Cenozoic, Pleistocene and Recent glaciomarine analogues

Ice-reworked foraminifera tests of Cretaceous–Cenozoic age occur in upper Pleistocene glaciomarine deposits in the Scotian Shelf and their presence increases deeper into the glaciomarine sequence (Scott and Medioli, 1988); these increases of ice-reworked test abundance are systematic and suggest that it is an index to the amount of erosive glacial activity taking place at the former ice margin. The increase in reworked forms occurred closer to the glacial maxima as the glacial grounding increases (Scott and Medioli, 1988). We observed the same pattern in the Barrika glaciation, where the amount of ice-rafted biodebris increases significantly during glacial maxima, coinciding with the evidence of grounding ice (Fig. 3) and thus resembling the glaciomarine dynamics and sedimentary responses of Late Pleistocene glaciations in Arctic Canada (cf. Scott and Medioli, 1988).

Reworked foraminifera tests are common in offshore Antarctic sediments (Quilty, 2001) where similar reworked multistriated foraminifera tests, including *Gyroidinoides cf. aequilateralis* (Plummer), *Globanomalina pseudomenardii* (Bolli), and *Cibicides succedens* (Brotzen), have been recovered from Holocene to early Cenozoic deposits in short gravity cores from the Mac. Robertson Shelf (see Plates 1 and 3 of Quilty, 2001).

The occurrence of reworked foraminifera in glaciomarine deposits is also described from offshore Antarctica. Foraminifera in ice-proximal diamict sediments from a backstepping grounding zone wedge (GZW) on the eastern Ross Sea continental shelf, Antarctica, exhibit physical damage, such as fractures and signs of erosion, indicating reworking from older sediments incorporated into diamictites (Bart et al., 2016). Similarly, reworked foraminifera occur in Ross Sea diamictites (Prothro et al., 2018) and alongside Cretaceous nannofossils, in Cenozoic glacial diamictites from Cape Lamb, Vega Island, Antarctica (Concheyro et al., 2014). Shelf-dwelling benthic foraminifera, including *Elphidium excavatum*, *Buccella frigida*, and *Islandiella helenae*, serve as key proxies for reconstructing past grounded ice extent and activity on the continental shelf (Jennings et al., 1996), marking their transport from the shelf to the continental slope around 11–10 ka, reflecting ice advances from Cumberland Sound (Jennings et al., 1996). Incorporation of other

microfossils to glaciomarine environments due local sources and glacial transport (Quilty et al., 1999) also include Cretaceous and Permian microfossils recovered from offshore cores from western Prydz Bay. The glaciomarine deposits of the Campanian glaciation contain reworked Cenomanian nannofossils that appear associated with IRD, IRDb, glacial dropstones and glaciomarine diamictites during glacial maxima, and during glacial minima associated with cool-water and high-latitude nannofossils taxa, IRDp and IRD (Fig. 3).

4.3. Facies Associations

4.3.1. Facies Association 1: distal glaciomarine environment

This facies association, [Fm-FI-Fm(d)-Fl(d)] (Figs. 7A and 8A–8J), represents sedimentation in a distal glaciomarine domain (Fig. 15B and 15C) (cf., Domack and Powell, 2018) (Supplementary Table 4). It is characterized by the accumulation of hemipelagic laminated marly facies containing cool-water/high-latitude nannofossils taxa (Fig. 5A), under an intense rainout of clasts from drifting and melting icebergs (Fig. 15B) (cf., Dowdeswell and Dowdeswell, 1989). It includes (i) multistriated ice-rafted debris (IRD) (Figs. 6, 7A and 8I and 8J, Supplementary Video 1) (e.g., Jaeger and Nittrouer, 1999; Hoffman and Schrag, 2002; Bailey et al., 2022; Rodríguez-López et al., 2024); (ii) multistriated ice-rafted dropstones (IRDp) (Figs. 8A–8J) (e.g., Anderson et al., 1996; Fielding et al., 2008; Le Heron, 2012, 2015; Le Heron et al., 2021; Rodríguez-López et al., 2024); and (iii) multistriated ice-rafted biodebris (IRDb) (ice-rafted multistriated foraminifera tests and Cenomanian nannofossils) (Fig. 7B–7G, Supplementary Video 2) (e.g., Jennings et al., 1996; Bart et al., 2016). This glaciomarine setting is represented by four lithofacies: (i) massive to silt-streaked dark grey marlstones (Fm); (ii) silt- to sand-laminated grey marlstones (FI); (iii) massive to silt-streaked dark grey marlstones with dropstones [Fm(d)]; and (iv) and finely laminated grey marlstones with dropstones [Fl(d)] (Figs. 7A, and 8A–8J) (Supplementary Table 4) (e.g., Eyles et al., 1983; Domack, 1984; Ó Cofaigh and Dowdeswell, 2001; Le Heron et al., 2019a; An et al., 2023). This facies association accumulated in a glaciomarine offshore environment below storm-wave base, where meter- to decameter-thick tabular intervals of fine-grained sediments accumulated by suspension settling from turbid overflow plumes (e.g., Ó Cofaigh and Dowdeswell, 2001), leading to preservation of horizontal and planar silt and sand lamination, but where melt out of drifting icebergs led to intense rain-out of till clasts from iceberg ice to the ocean floor (Fig. 15B and 15C) (e.g., Martin, 1999; Le Heron et al., 2009; Fallgatter and Paim, 2019).

These laminated fine-grained distal marine deposits contain iceberg-rafted sediments (cf., Bailey et al., 2022), including (i) scattered striated and faceted ice-rafted glacial dropstones (IRDp) (Fig. 8B, 8E and 8F), (ii) ice-rafted debris (IRD) (Fig. 6C, 6G, 6L and 6P), and (iii) multistriated and abraded ice-rafted bio-debris (IRDb) (Fig. 7B–7E), all of them evidence of superimposed multidirectional subglacial abrasion (cf., Le Heron, 2007; Le Heron and Craig, 2008; Tofaif et al., 2019) on multi-scale till clasts prior to their incorporation into drifting icebergs delivered from glacier calving fronts. The dropstones occur as dispersed striated and faceted outsized clasts with polished edges (cf., Bozzano et al., 2021), faceted surfaces, and cross-cutting striations (cf., Brezinski et al., 2010; Le Heron, 2015; Chen et al., 2021) (Figs. 7A, 8A–8J). Ice-rafted dropstones are polymictic (limestones, sandstones, flint, and Albian to Jurassic volcanics) pebble- to cobble-size clasts (0.4 cm to 16 cm in diameter) scattered in the fine-grained laminated marlstones, similar in size and shape to the sand- and gravel-sized ice-rafted debris reported from the southwest Atlantic Ocean (Bornhold, 1983). The dropstones generated impact structures beneath them as consequence of the rain out from melting icebergs (cf., Condon et al., 2002; Le Heron, 2012; Le Heron et al., 2017; Eidam et al., 2019; Xia et al., 2023), leading to (i) disruption and reduced thickness of the underlying lamination (e.g., Le Heron, 2015; Rodríguez-López et al., 2024), (ii) downturning of the host stratification and lamination by up to 90° (Limarino et al.,

2002), and (iii) truncation of stratification and lamination (Wu and Rodríguez-López, 2021) (Fig. 8A–8H). Undisturbed laminated clays and siltstones above the dropstones represent subsequent draping lamination covering the protruding part of the glacial dropstones (Fig. 8B, 8C and 8H) (cf., Thomas and Connell, 1985; Rocha-Campos et al., 2008; McGee et al., 2012; Rodríguez-López et al., 2016, 2024; Griffis et al., 2023).

4.3.2. Facies Association 2: outer proximal glaciomarine environment

This facies association [Fm(d)-Fl(d)-Dmm(d)-Dms(d)-Sl-Sr] (Figs. 9 and 10A–C) represents sedimentation in a more proximal glaciomarine domain (Fig. 15B and 15D) (e.g., Domack and Powell, 2018) than distal glaciomarine facies association 1 (cf., Spence et al., 2016; Le Heron et al., 2022a) (Supplementary Table 4). The association is characterized by sedimentation controlled by glacier calving, meltwater plumes, and rainout of ice-rafted debris and dropstones from drifting icebergs (cf., Smith and Andrews, 2000) in an ice-margin proximal location (Fig. 15B) (e.g., Dowdeswell et al., 1998; Vesely et al., 2015; Hoffman et al., 2017; Malone et al., 2023). This association is characterized by dm-thick intervals formed by interbedded massive and laminated marlstones with ice-rafted debris and large striated dropstones [Fm(d)-Fl(d)] interbedded with thin glaciomarine turbidites (lithofacies [Sr-Sl]) (Fig. 9A–9F).

This facies association also contains rain out diamictites from drifting icebergs, forming massive and stratified diamictites that contain ice-rafted debris and ice-rafted dropstones [Dmm(d)-Dms(d)] (cf., Lepp et al., 2022), both at cm- and m-scale (Fig. 10A–10C) interbedded with IRD-free layers. Ice-rafted dropstones are striated and faceted and show their long axis oriented at high angles to bedding (cf., Isbell, 2010) (Figs. 9E, 9F, 10A and 10B). The IRDp are striated and polymictic, including Albian to Jurassic clasts (Fig. 9C), and flint and limestone clasts. These ice-rafted dropstones from the Barrika glaciation show exceptionally well-preserved impact structures on seabed sediments, puncturing them (Figs. 9B and 9D, 10A–10C), and creating deep impact structures affecting the underlying marlstone lithofacies (Fig. 9E and 9F), resembling other well-known glacial successions worldwide (e.g., Thomas and Connell, 1985; Hoffman and Schrag, 2002; Hoffmann et al., 2004; Le Heron et al., 2014a; Le Heron, 2015). In detail, the impact structures on the ocean floor produced by the drop and fall of these ice-rafted dropstones from icebergs led to: (i) disruption/puncturing and thickness reduction of the underlying lamination (e.g., Le Heron, 2015; Baioumy et al., 2020; Rodríguez-López et al., 2024) (Fig. 9A, 9B and 9D); (ii) downwarping and bending of the host stratification and lamination by up to 90° (Fig. 9A–9F) (cf., Limarino et al., 2002; Cox et al., 2013; Le Heron and Busfield, 2016); and (iii) truncation and piercing of stratification and lamination (Figs. 9A, 9B, 9D–9F and 10A and 10B) associated with the drop of till clasts from melting icebergs (Fig. 15B) (e.g., Le Heron et al., 2014b; Busfield and Le Heron, 2016; Wu and Rodríguez-López, 2021). The ice-rafted dropstones from Barrika are overlapped by overlying laminated clays and siltstones (e.g., Brezinski et al., 2010) (Fig. 9B, 9D–9F and 10A–10C) representing subsequent draping lamination covering the protruding part of the glacial dropstones (cf., Griffis et al., 2023; Rodríguez-López et al., 2024) after dropstone drop from the iceberg and impact on the ocean floor (e.g., Thomas and Connell, 1985; McGee et al., 2012; Rodríguez-López et al., 2016). These onlapping laminated marlstones contain cool-water and high-latitude nannofossils (Fig. 5A) and ice-rafted debris (IRD) with striations and conchoidal fractures (Fig. 6). The protruding part of the striated ice-rafted dropstones is sharply covered by glaciomarine sandy turbidites postdating glacial rainout periods (Fig. 9A–9F); locally IRD and IRDp intervals are interbedded with thin laminated varved intervals, formed by siliciclastic and mixed-siliciclastic and carbonate varvites (plumites), and with glacial diamictites with IRD and IRDp. This architecture is like that described in glaciomarine facies from the

Permian Metschel Tillite, southern Victoria Land, Antarctica (Isbell, 2010), which commonly form in both polar and temperate glaciomarine systems (Isbell, 2010), where IRDp intervals are sandwiched between non-deformed parallel strata, below formed by varvites (plumites) (e.g., Isbell et al., 2023) and overlying glacial turbidite lobes (lithofacies Sl and Sr), preserving the original stratification planes So, onlapping the protruding abraded and striated ice-rafted clasts (cf., Isbell, 2010). The sandy glacioturbidites covering the glaciomarine deposits with IRDp and IRD (Fig. 9A–9F) were derived from grounding-line fans due to meltwater discharge from a turbulent jet at the base of a glacier (cf. Powell, 1990); these meltwater-derived fluxes prograde in the proglacial marine realm covering the ice-rafted dropstones (Fig. 9A–9F, 15B) (Isbell, 2010). In both glaciomarine systems, the Permian from Antarctica, and the Cretaceous Barrika glaciation, the occurrence of abundant stratified diamictites with dropstones [Dms(d)] points to sedimentation occurring both from settling of particles from buoyant low-density meltwater plumes (Isbell, 2010) and drifting icebergs; in this setting, the striated and faceted dropstones fall down to the ocean floor from englacial bands in the ice fronts and/or from debris bands in drifting icebergs in a proximal glaciomarine environment (cf., Eyles and McCabe, 1989; Powell and Cooper, 2002; Isbell, 2010) (Fig. 15A and 15B). This facies association from the Campanian of Barrika evidence sedimentation in proximal glaciomarine settings as those from polar and temperate glaciomarine systems (e.g., Powell and Molnia, 1989; Mangerud and Svendsen, 1990; Isbell, 2010) as consequence of the ongoing fragmentation, tilting and overturning of icebergs rich in debris bands (see Fig. 2 of Woodworth-Lynas et al., 1991) that lead to periodic sedimentation events characterized by dumping of ice-rafted clasts into open waters (Fig. 15A and 15B) (e.g., Drewry and Cooper, 1981; Thomas and Connell, 1985) resembling the “bergstone mud facies” of Hambrey and Glasser (2012).

Faceted, abraded and striated bullet-shaped ice-rafted dropstones during the Barrika glaciation dropped and dumped off the glacier ice as it calved (e.g., Powell, 1981) during intense ice mélanges (e.g., Amundson et al., 2010) and overturning of large icebergs, dropping dropstones and producing impact structures and puncturing on glaciomarine marlstones (Figs. 9 and 10) being overlapped by tabular massive diamictites with dropstones and marlstones with ice-rafted debris and dropstones as the proximal glaciomarine sedimentary dynamics progressed (e.g., Isbell, 2010). Similar processes have been described as dumpstones linked with flipping out icebergs (Pisarska-Jamrozko et al., 2018) and melt-out of endglacial sediments (Fig. 15B). Some ice-rafted dropstones in the Barrika glacial deposits are more than 1.5 m long, which are half the size of the observed ice-rafted blocks (of more than 3 m long) that we report from drifting icebergs in offshore Antarctica (Fig. 15A). This Cretaceous facies association shows evidence of features and dynamics comparable to those glaciomarine systems those from Neoproterozoic glaciomarine deposits (Hoffman and Schrag, 2002; Arnaud and Etienne, 2011) and those associated with the Baltic Ice Stream during the Weichselian glaciation (Funen Island, Denmark) (Jørgensen and Piotrowski, 2003). The glaciomarine deposits of the Barrika glaciation share similarities with outsized abraded and striated glacial clasts with long-axis perpendicular to stratification planes showing impact structures and being draped by lithofacies Fl(d) laminated marlstones with IRDp and IRD dropped from melting icebergs described by Eyles et al. (1998) and Koch and Isbell (2013). The large rounded and faceted ice-rafted boulder-size dropstones with their long-axis oriented vertically and showing strong underlying impact structures and drapes by overlying lamination from the Campanian Barrika glaciation (Fig. 9E and 9F) are very similar to the glaciomarine dropstones described by Hart and Roberts (1994) from the Quaternary glaciomarine site (Melabakkar-Asbakkar, Iceland). The intense glacial-rainout intervals in the Barrika glaciation are similar to those reported from the Neoproterozoic of County Donegal, Ireland (cf., Condon et al., 2002) and

the occurrence of local minor slump snouts interbedded with these lithofacies could be linked with icebergs calving as those described by Powell (1983).

Collectively, this facies association evidences sedimentation in an active calving front of tidewater glaciers (Fig. 15B) where diamictites with dropstones and interbedded marlstones contain cool-water and high-latitude nannofossils and ice-rafted debris (Fig. 2). Similar striated and faceted ice-rafted dropstones and associated lithofacies, as those from Barrika in Spain, are reported in well-known deep time glaciomarine systems (e.g., Huuse et al., 2012; Le Heron et al., 2014b, 2020a), including the Neoproterozoic of Namibia (Domack and Hoffman, 2011), the Sturtian glaciation from the Cryogenian of South Australia (Busfield and Le Heron, 2014) and from glaciomarine deposits from the Mississippian Río Blanco Basin, Argentina (Ezpeleta et al., 2020).

In more distal settings of this proximal glaciomarine realm of the Barrika glaciation, sedimentation is characterized by tabular cm-thick strata formed by massive to laminated diamictites with IRD and IRDp interbedded with cm-thick IRD-free intervals (Fig. 10A–10C). This is evidence of recurrent iceberg rainout intervals (e.g., Eyles et al., 1993) separated by hemipelagic, dropstone-free lithologies recording periods devoid of glacial rainout (Fig. 10A–10C) (e.g. Condon et al., 2002). These lithofacies from Barrika mirror the paucity observed in glaciomarine systems from the Neoproterozoic glaciations (e.g., Condon and Prave, 2000; Condon et al., 2002) and those from Scoresby Sund, East Greenland, where laminated muddy facies without IRD (FI) are abruptly bracketed by IRD-rich diamictites [Dmm(d)] (Ó Cofaigh and Dowdeswell, 2001) as a consequence of alternating suspension sedimentation from meltwater plumes and iceberg rafting (Ó Cofaigh and Dowdeswell, 2001). Similar couplets of these from the Barrika glaciation defined by interbedded diamictites with intense rainout of ice-rafted dropstones and ice-rafted debris [Dmm(d)] and laminated muds with minor ice-rafted debris [FI(d)] (Fig. 10A–10C) have been reported from the Disenchantment Bay, Southern Alaska (Cowan et al., 1997); there, the accumulation of ice-rafted debris is constant throughout the year but accumulation of diamicton with ice-rafted debris (the lithofacies [Dmm(d)] in Barrika, Fig. 10A–10C) is only occurring during intense rainout intervals in winter when longer resident time of icebergs in the proglacial glaciomarine environment occur (Cowan et al., 1997).

4.3.3. Facies Association 3: inner proximal glaciomarine to subglacial environment

4.3.3.1. Undermelt diamictites. This facies association, [Dmm(d)-Dms(d)-Dms(d)(s)-Dms(s)-glacial rafts] (Supplementary Table 4), represents sedimentation in proximal glaciomarine environments beneath the calving zone and the ice shelf of tidewater glaciers, but close enough to the ice-sediment contact zone for being episodically affected by the advance of the grounding line of these glaciers (Fig. 15B and 15E) (e.g., Ives and Isbell, 2023), that led to a sustained subglacial bulldozing of striated glacial rafts (cf., Rütther et al., 2013; Ottesen et al., 2016). The record of this facies association evidences a fluctuating grounding line (Fig. 15B and 15E) affecting glaciomarine proximal lithofacies showing ice-rafted dropstones dropping and dumping off from icebergs beneath an active calving zone, and in immediately proximal areas to floating ice (ice shelves) where sustained rainout from melting debris-rich ice occurred forming undermelt diamicton (*sensu* Giles et al., 2017) (e.g., Gibbard, 1980; Gravenor et al., 1984; Powell, 1984). These undermelt diamictites in the Barrika Formation occur as massive to stratified diamictites with preserved faceted dropstones [Dmm(d)-Dms(d)] (Figs. 10–12 and Supplementary Video 4): these dropstones are bullet-shaped IRDp (Fig. 10E and 10F) and large angular IRDp (Fig. 12) showing impact structures and associated puncturing and downturned lamination (Fig. 10E, 10F and 12). Their long axes are oriented vertically with respect to depositional surface (S_0), being covered by draping diamictite lamination (Figs. 10E, 10F and 12A–12C). These undermelt

diamictites with dropstones can form due to ice-rafted debris dropping from icebergs (e.g., Dowdeswell et al., 1994; Henry et al., 2012; Le Heron et al., 2014b) and associated dumping (e.g., Thomas and Connell, 1985) but also with fall of till clasts from floating ice shelf near the grounding zone, that could deliver an abundance of glacial clasts by rainout (Fig. 15B) (e.g., Le Heron et al., 2022b; López Gamundi, 2024).

These undermelt diamictites (cf., Giles et al., 2017) with IRDp formed by an intense rainout of fine-grained sediments from meltwater plumes and the drop of subglacial clasts located beneath the ice shelf (Fig. 15B). These undermelt diamictites contain glacial clasts with evidence of subglacial abrasion stage (before being deposited as ice-rafted dropstones), including facets, cross-cutting multistriations, and stoss-and-lee morphologies (Figs. 10E and 10F, 11A–11I) (e.g., Evans et al., 2006; Menzies et al., 2018). These features indicate an active transfer of subglacial clasts occurring in the termini of the Barrika glaciation's tidewater glaciers to the floating ice of the tidewater glaciers. Some of these undermelt diamictite clasts contain evidence of sustained subglacial erosion and subglacial ploughing that, for the first time is observed at SEM scale (Fig. 11F and 11G), mirroring those subglacial striations and grooves at outcrop scale (cf., O'Brien and Christie-Blick, 1992; Le Heron, 2016; Wohlschlägl et al., 2023). Glacial erosion features in deep time shows fractal behaviour; the ploughed groove reported from the Paleozoic glaciation of Saudi Arabia (Sarah Formation) (cf., Le Heron et al., 2020b) constitutes a good macroscale outcrop analogue of this SEM example from the Barrika glaciation.

4.3.3.2. Subglacial traction tillites. This facies association also shows evidence of subglacial ploughing, sliding and lodgement (cf., Evans et al., 2006) in the subglacial traction zone/ice-bed interface (Fig. 15B) (cf., Giles et al., 2017). It is characterized by slightly sheared diamictites with ploughed dropstones [Dmm(d)(s)] (Figs. 11 and 12), massive and stratified diamictites with multistriated bullet-shaped glacial clasts (Fig. 13), large striated and grooved glacial rafts (Fig. 14), all of them interbedded and draped with intervals of horizontal non-deformed finely laminated marlstones with dropstones [FI(d)] and with intervals of massive diamictites with dropstones [Dmm(d)] (Giles et al., 2017) (Fig. 14C and 14E).

These undermelt diamictites or ice-proximal rainout tillites containing ice-rafted dropstones [Dmm(d)-Dms(d)] (e.g., Le Heron et al., 2019a) from the ice shelf (Fig. 11 and 12) (cf., Cowan et al., 2012; Le Heron et al., 2022a; López Gamundi, 2024) were overridden during forthcoming periods of glacier advance (Fig. 15B). These subglacial traction tillites/diamictites formed as the ice-push and shear led to the incorporation of proglacial glaciomarine diamictites and glaciomarine muds with ice-rafted debris and dropstones into the subglacial zone (Fig. 15B) (e.g., Evans and Twigg, 2002; Evans et al., 2006; Giles et al., 2017) as previously described by Boulton et al. (1996) in recent systems. This incorporation below the grounding line by subglacial sliding induced subtle deformation to the till structure associated with subglacial shear (cf., Cowan et al., 2012), evolving into [Dmm(d)(s)] and [Dms(d)(s)] lithofacies (e.g., Eyles et al., 1983) forming pseudo-laminated tillites *sensu* Giles et al. (2017). The glaciomarine sediments were smeared due to an advancing glacier being sheared as a deforming carpet of glaciomarine muds (Boulton et al., 1996). These subglacial traction tillites [Dmm(d)(s)] and [Dms(d)(s)] of the Barrika Formation (Supplementary Table 4) shows common smudges defined by ploughed multistriated, faceted and abraded bullet-shaped clasts (stoss-and-lee clasts) (Figs. 11 and 12) (e.g., Evans et al., 2006). These ploughed clasts at different scales (1 in Fig. 11D and 11I), appear associated with (i) pressure shadows (2 in Fig. 11D, and 3 in Fig. 11I) (e.g., Busfield and Le Heron, 2013, 2016; Kettler et al., 2023); (ii) dispersion tails (Fig. 12A and 12C) (Piotrowski and Kraus, 1997; Evans et al., 2006); (iii) rotated (galaxies) clasts and structures (4 in Figs. 11D and 11I) (cf., Van der Meer et al., 2003; Phillips et al., 2013) all of them evidence of subglacial shear and lodgement (e.g., Eyles et al., 1994; Piotrowski et al., 2001) on

these subglacial traction tillites (cf., Giles et al., 2017).

The subglacial diamictites from the Barrika glaciation are very similar to the subglacial features observed in Palaeoproterozoic glaciomarine diamictites from the the Carajás Basin (Brazil) (Araújo and Nogueira, 2019) and Neoproterozoic glacial diamictites from California (Kettler et al., 2023). These small-scale sheared diamictites with dropstones lithofacies [Dmm(d)(s)-Dms(d)(s)] from the Barrika Formation are very similar to the subglacially sheared diamictites (cf., Boulton et al., 2001; Le Heron et al., 2013) from the Neoproterozoic Snowball Earth Ghauf glaciation (Namibia) (cf., Domack and Hoffman, 2011) and shares similarities with shearing due to iceberg keel ploughing (cf., Domack and Hoffman, 2011; Rodríguez-López et al., 2021). The occurrence of erosion tails (Fig. 12A and 12C) and boudins demonstrate deformation in a subglacial shear zone at the ice-soft subglacial sediment interface (e.g., Piotrowski and Kraus, 1997; Piotrowski et al., 2001; Evans et al., 2006; Giles et al., 2017). The record of the Barrika glaciation contains subglacial ploughed multistriated and faceted clasts similar to those reported by Boulton (1978) showing superimposed facets (compare the glacial clast from subglacial traction tillite in Fig. 11B–11D, with the glacially abraded clast in fig. 6c of Boulton, 1978).

4.3.3.3. Subglacial clasts in proximal and subglacial diamictites. The glacial diamictites of Barrika contains exceptionally preserved glacially abraded clasts. They include (i) faceted smoothed, and multistriated clasts (Fig. 13A–13E) (e.g., Boulton, 1978; Jones and Fielding, 2008; Evans et al., 2012; Caputo and dos Santos, 2020), showing cross-cutting multidirectional striation sets (Supplementary Video 3) (cf., Le Heron et al., 2011; Le Heron et al., 2014a, 2014b, 2022b; Menzies et al., 2018; Tofaif et al., 2019; Vandyk et al., 2019); (ii) ploughed bullet-shaped striated clasts (Fig. 13F) (e.g., Sokolowski and Wysota, 2020); (iii) flat-iron/bullet-shaped subglacial clasts with deep striated grooves (Fig. 13G); these striations often show evidence of being covered by successive sediment flows, similar to those in the Early Palaeozoic Sarah Formation in Saudi Arabia (e.g., Le Heron et al., 2018, 2019b); (iv) striated bullet-shaped clasts (Fig. 13H) (e.g., Fedorchuk et al., 2019; Dietrich et al., 2021; Chen et al., 2021; Mottin et al., 2023) featuring cross-cutting multistriated surfaces covered by the diamictite matrix, closely resembling striated surfaces found in Permo–Carboniferous diamictites from the Transatlantic Mountains in Antarctica (e.g., Miller, 1989) and those from the Neoproterozoic Snowball Earth (e.g., Hoffman and Schrag, 2002); and (v) subglacial lee-and-stoss clasts showing abrasion (A) and fracture (F) margins (Fig. 13I) (e.g., Evans et al., 2006) showing striations coherent with the ice displacement indicated by the abrasion-fracture sides orientations (Fig. 13I).

The multistriated subglacial clasts of the Barrika glaciation have been previously described from glaciomarine diamictites of the Upper Proterozoic Vestertana Group in Northern Norway (e.g., Edwards, 1984), from Neoproterozoic glacial diamictites of California (e.g., Busfield and Le Heron, 2016), and striated boulders within proglacial debris margin of the Stein Glacier (Switzerland) (e.g., Menzies et al., 2018). Further comparisons are evident with similar glacial diamictites with multistriated faceted and bullet-shaped clasts have been reported from the Dwyka glacial rocks in southern Namibia (e.g., Le Heron et al., 2022b) and from the Cryogenian Sturtian glaciation (Chuosi Formation, Namibia) (see Fig. 6c of Le Heron et al., 2013) as well as with the Carboniferous glaciomarine records from Argentina (e.g., Ezpeleta et al., 2020).

4.3.3.4. Subglacial bulldozing of glacial rafts. This facies association also shows evidence of subglacial ploughing of large glacial rafts (e.g., Rütther et al., 2013; Ottesen et al., 2016) (Fig. 14A–14G) that are surrounded and draped by massive diamictites and stratified diamictites containing dropstones and subglacial diamictites with multistriated and faceted clasts (Figs. 13 and 14G). These glacial clast forms pavements showing multistriated bullet-shaped clasts (Fig. 14G) in massive

subglacial traction tillites/diamictites [Dmm-Dmm(s)] (e.g., Giles et al., 2017). Associated glacially striated boulder rafts rest on glacially abraded substrates forming grooves with paraxial ridges structures (Fig. 14C–14E) as those observed in subglacial recent counterparts (cf., Evans et al., 2021). The transport of these subglacial rafts was associated with glacial advances (cf., Rütther et al., 2013; Ottesen et al., 2016) that formed pavements of glacial striated boulders in the Barrika glaciation (Fig. 15B) (cf., Edwards, 1984; Eyles, 1988; Giles et al., 2017). The glacially striated and abraded boulders from the Barrika Formation show the long-axis oriented parallel to the striation directions, parallel to the prow and groove directions on adjacent rafts from the diamictites, and parallel to the striations from other flat-iron and bullet-shaped clasts from the overlapping diamictites, suggesting a common ice-stream displacement direction (e.g., Le Heron, 2016). The immediately underlying sedimentary strata are not deformed, showing horizontal stratification planes (S_0), being the deformation linked with the subglacial drag of the raft on the underlying semi-consolidated sedimentary substrate (Fig. 14C). The subglacial ploughing and dragging of this raft led to intense abrasion of the lateral ridge (Fig. 14C and 14E) and a clear banded berm or ridge (Fig. 14C and 14D). The 4 m glacial raft shows surfaces of abrasion and striations; in particular, the base of the glacial raft shows striations (Fig. 14C and 14F), while the upper abraded surfaces of these rafts show parallel prow and groove systems (Fig. 14A and 14B), evidence of subglacial ploughing and erosion due to subglacial transport of these rafts and clasts (cf., Piotrowski et al., 2001). These linear grooves with associated frontal sediment prows on striated surfaces of the clasts, boulders, and rafts (Fig. 14A and 14B) is evidence of subglacial clasts being pushed through the glacier substrate in the glacier sole (cf., Boulton, 1979), being actively ploughed through the semi-consolidated to soft deformable bed (e.g., Clark and Hansel, 1989; Iverson and Hooyer, 2004). The exceptional preservation of clasts ploughed at the end of the grooves, surrounded by the lee-side arched prow (Fig. 14A and 14B) is evidence of clast penetration resistance to the shear deformation of the ice flow (e.g., Clark and Hansel, 1989). This is strong evidence of subglacial bulldozing (e.g., Boulton, 1976; Boulton et al., 2001; Christoffersen et al., 2005) leading to prow formation down-glacier, and grooves pointing out up-glacier (e.g., Iverson and Hooyer, 2004). Similar subglacial prow-and-groove structures due to subglacial ploughing at the ice–till interface as those reported from the Campanian Barrika glaciation have been described from (i) the Paleozoic glacial systems of Brazil (cf., Trosdorf Jr. et al., 2005; Vesely et al., 2015); (ii) the Pleistocene of Illinois (cf., Thomason and Iverson, 2008) and (iii) the Pleistocene of Poland (cf., Krzyszkowski, 1994) and Denmark (cf., Jørgensen and Piotrowski, 2003). Collectively, these glacial rafts (Fig. 14A–14G) form the most basal part of the lodgement till (cf., Eyles et al., 1982) constituting blocks rubble facies produced by the intense plucking of the frontal and lateral edges of rock drumlins (pre-Campanian substrate in Barrika) and the subsequent melt-out of the rubble-rich basal debris across the hard bed (e.g., Eyles and Lazorek, 2014; Eyles and Doughty, 2016). This is evidence of a drumlinized and megagrooved ‘hard bed’ (e.g., Eyles and Doughty, 2016), associated with the subglacial erosion of Campanian palaeo-ice streams on previous Cretaceous sedimentary series (Figs. 14 and 15B).

5. The Barrika tidewater glacier model and dynamics

The Barrika glaciation shows a glaciomarine record similar to other Phanerozoic and Proterozoic global glaciations (Fig. 15A–15E) (e.g., Powell, 1981, 1984; Visser, 1997; Smith and Andrews, 2000; Domack and Powell, 2018; Dowdeswell et al., 2019). The similarities include (i) the well-known Carboniferous glaciomarine systems (e.g., Isbell et al., 2008, 2012, 2021), (ii) the recently discovered Palaeoproterozoic glaciomarine deposits from the Carajás Basin (Amazon Craton, Brazil) (cf., Araújo and Nogueira, 2019), (iii) glaciomarine depositional systems associated with recessive and extensive marine ice sheets at the end of the Late Palaeozoic Glaciation (e.g., Von Brunn and Gravenor, 1983), as

well as (iv) the Upper Proterozoic glaciomarine record from Vestertana Group in northern Norway (e.g., Edwards, 1984). The Campanian glaciomarine system of the Barrika glaciation share similarities with all of them, including: (i) a proximal glaciomarine and glacially influenced marine deposits with striated boulder pavements resulting from grounded ice advance (cf., Isbell et al., 2012); in the Campanian Barrika case includes striated and abraded glacial rafts overlapped by subglacial diamictites (Fig. 14); (ii) thick stratified and massive diamictites accumulated due to a combination of iceberg rafting and meltwater plumes (cf., Isbell et al., 2012), in Barrika showing a clear pattern of multi-episodic calving of the tidewater glaciers fronts; (iii) wedge-shaped sandstone bodies deposited as grounding-line fans (e.g., Isbell et al., 2012) which are onlapping ice-rafted dropstones encased in marine marlstones after a period of glacial-rainout; and (iv) multistriated IRDp deposited in distal marine environments (cf., Isbell et al., 2012), containing in the case of Barrika glaciation, an association of faceted and striated ice-rafted dropstones (IRDp), angular and multi-striated ice-rafted debris (IRD), and multi-striated ice-rafted biodebris (IRDb).

In detail, the proximal–distal pattern of the Campanian Barrika glaciation (Fig. 15B–15E) resembles the one described by Marcos et al. (2018) for the Carboniferous glaciomarine system of the Cushamen Formation, western North Patagonian Massif in Argentina (see Fig. 7 of ref. Marcos et al., 2018). The Barrika Formation contains the record of repeated expansion of a partially floating ice shelves of tidewater glaciers to the edge of the Atlantic continental shelf during the early Campanian with evidence of pulsed icebergs delivery (Fig. 15B) (e.g., Le Heron and Busfield, 2016) driven by low-latitude Cretaceous ice-cap dynamics and overriding of ice-marginal glaciomarine deposits being incorporated as subglacial till in the sole of advancing tidewater glaciers (e.g., Ó Cofaigh et al., 2011). The widespread occurrence of exceptionally preserved impact structures associated with ice-rafted clasts and dropstones at all scales (from multistriated mm- ice-rafted debris (IRD) to pebble to large boulder-sized dropstones (IRDp) is indicative of intensive *in-situ* rainout of ice-rafted clasts from icebergs linked to an unstable ice front enhancing calving and icebergs distribution (e.g., Busfield and Le Heron, 2016) probably forming ice *mélange* and iceberg jams in front of the ice shelf (Fig. 15B). Evidence of an advancing and retreating grounding line in the shelf, incorporating proglacial glaciomarine sediments into the subglacial realm leading to subglacial till and glacial raft as well as local glacioclastic lobes suggesting a pivoting ice stream line with evidence of coeval distal glaciomarine settings, an active grounding zone wedge associated with coeval calving zone in the ice front, and subglacial deformation zone (see Fig. 3 of Eyles et al., 1985). The Barrika glaciation sedimentary record contains all the elements described by Smith et al. (2019) in their extensive review on the marine geological imprint of Antarctic ice shelves (Fig. 15B). The macro-, meso-, and micro- glacial erosional features reported from the subglacial facies and ice-rafted dropstones are mirroring those reported worldwide from subglacial deformation beds associated with advancing glaciers (e.g., Le Heron et al., 2020b).

6. Discussion

6.1. A low-latitude anomaly in a greenhouse world; a comparison with recent lowest latitudinal tidewater glaciers

The discovery of evidence for extreme glaciation during the Late Cretaceous, extending to a palaeolatitude of 35°N in northern Iberia, challenges conventional views of the Cretaceous as a uniformly warm greenhouse period. This glaciation was associated with a palaeomassif (Iberian Massif) spanning approximately 300,000 km² (Fig. 16B and 16F). To contextualize these findings, we compare the Barrika glaciation with modern low-latitude tidewater glaciers at Kerguelen (49.54°S) (Fig. 16C), South Georgia (~54.45°S) (Fig. 16D), and Bouvet (54.20°S) (Fig. 16E), which represent the lowest-latitude extent of contemporary tidewater glaciation (Fig. 16G–16I), and with the extent of both the

Southern and Northern Patagonian Ice Stream (52°–46°S) (Fig. 16A). This approach can be used as a baseline for comparison for highlights the climatic and palaeogeographic factors that may have facilitated glaciation at such low palaeolatitudes in the Cretaceous providing insights into the potential scale and environmental implications of the Barrika Ice Cap (Fig. 16).

Modern tidewater glaciers at Kerguelen, Bouvet, and South Georgia exist in sub-Antarctic climates characterized by mean annual temperatures between 3.9°C and -1°C and high precipitation, conditions conducive to glacier formation and persistence where tidewater glaciers interact with ocean waters (Kerguelen island, Cook Ice Cap in the southern Indian Ocean, and the Bouvert Island Ice Cap and the South Georgia Ice Cap in the southern Atlantic Ocean). The Cook Ice Cap on Kerguelen, covering 410 km² today (Verfaillie et al., 2021) at 1,050 m.a.s.l., supports tidewater glaciers in fjords (Fig. 16C and 16G). Similarly, South Georgia's glaciers, covering ~ 2,457 km² (Fig. 16D and 16H), extended to the continental shelf during the LGM (White et al., 2018). Bouvet Island, though smaller (~50 km² of ice cover), sustains tidewater glaciers due to its cold, wet climate (Fig. 16E and 16I) (Thomas et al., 2021). These glaciers, situated at 49°S to 54°S, are sustained by sub-Antarctic conditions, which contrast sharply with the warmer, subtropical climates modelled and estimate for the Late Cretaceous (Judd et al., 2024).

The Barrika glaciation, occurring at 35°N, represents a palaeolatitudinal anomaly, as it is ~14–19° closer to the equator than these modern analogues (Fig. 16). The modern glaciers' crustal areas, of 50 km² (Bouvet Island Ice Cap), 410 km² (Cook Ice Cap, Kerguelen Island), and 2,457 km² (South Georgia Ice Cap) in their present state, are dwarfed by the 300,000 km² palaeomassif associated with the Barrika glaciation, though we have no evidence that the whole region was glaciated. Even accounting for LGM expansions (White et al., 2018), the Barrika palaeomassif suggests the potential for one or more ice caps substantially larger than modern sub-Antarctic glaciers. This disparity underscores the need to identify the climatic mechanisms that enabled such extensive glaciation at mid-latitudes during a greenhouse period. The presence of a 300,000 km² palaeomassif (Fig. 16B and 16F), likely an elevated highland, would have lowered temperatures through adiabatic cooling, potentially bringing mean annual temperatures closer to 0°C at higher elevations, similar to the sub-Antarctic conditions observed today.

The palaeolatitudinal position of the Barrika glaciation at 35°N, combined with the vast area of the palaeomassif, suggests that an ice cap (s) in the Iberian region could have been significantly larger than modern sub-Antarctic glaciers (Fig. 16). Considering a fully glaciated 300,000 km² palaeomassif in the Campanian, its size could equal a 1/5 of the Greenland ice sheet, hosting 17.5 times the total glaciated area of both the Northern (3,976 km²) and Southern Patagonian Ice fields (13,219 km²) (Millan et al., 2019) (Fig. 16A) implying the potential for regionally extensive ice cover in the form of extensive ice sheets that would explain the long term presence (1.84 Myr) of tidewater glaciers during the early Campanian in northern Iberia, with glacial maxima-minima every ~360 kyr (Fig. 3). Unlike the modern tidewater glaciers, which are constrained by small island topographies or narrow continental shelves, the Barrika palaeomassif's size and elevation likely supported continental-scale ice caps with tidewater margins, particularly if sea levels were lower due to glacioeustatic effects (Fig. 16). In terms of cryospheric processes, the Cretaceous tidewater glaciers (Fig. 15B) behaved similar to its Cenozoic-Quaternary counterparts, characterized by active calving fronts interacting with oceanic waters (Fig. 16G and 16I) delivering large icebergs (Fig. 16H).

The presence of such ice cap in Iberia would have profound palaeoenvironmental impacts; in this regard, and comparing with recent analogues, the interaction of tidewater glaciers with Late Cretaceous oceans may have influenced regional ocean circulation (e.g. Starr et al., 2021), and the melting of these Cretaceous icebergs could have affected the heat flux towards major tidewater glaciers in Iberia, as nowadays

Fig. 16. Comparison of lowest-latitude ice caps and tidewater glaciers, and the Southern and Northern Patagonian Ice Fields with the Iberian Massif close to the Cretaceous Barrika glaciation. (A) Southern and Northern Patagonian ice fields. (B) The Barrika glaciation outlet developed when continental crust was cropping out in an approximate area of $\sim 300,000 \text{ km}^2$ (Iberian Massif, including the basement of the current Cenozoic Duero Basin). The comparison with three current lowest latitudinal tidewater glaciers on Earth including the (C) Kerguelen Island (Cook Ice Cap, Southern Indian Ocean); (D), South Georgia (South Georgia Ice Cap, Southern Atlantic Ocean); and, (E) Bouvet Island Ice Cap (Southern Atlantic Ocean) exemplifies the palaeocontinental crust area prone to host extensive Cretaceous ice caps feeding the tidewater glaciers in Barrika (northern continental margin of Iberia). Satellite imagery from Google Earth (Data SIO, NOAA, U.S. Navy, NGA, GEBCO; Image Landsat / Copernicus). (F) Geological map from (Rodríguez-Fernández et al., 2015). Mapa Geológico de España a escala 1:1.000.000. © CN Instituto Geológico y Minero de España (IGME) (visited 13/05/2025). https://info.igme.es/cartografiadigital/geologica/Geologicos1MMapa.aspx?Id=Geologico1000_ (2015)&language=es. Pink colours mark the outcrops of the Proterozoic-Paleozoic rocks of the Iberian Massif and yellow marks the Cenozoic Duero basin, both for reference (Modified after Rodríguez-Fernández et al., 2015). (G) Tidewater glacier in one of the outlets of the Cook Ice Cap (Kerguelen Island) in the Southern Indian Ocean showing glacier crevasses conforming a calving front releasing icebergs to sea waters. (H) Tidewater glacier in a glacier from the South Georgia Ice Cap, South Atlantic Ocean showing meltwater fluxes mixing with marine waters, growlers and icebergs. (I) Calving front of the Bouvet Island Ice Cap.

occur in major Greenlandic tidewater glaciers (e.g. Davison et al., 2020). Moisture sources of this ice cap would have been the adjacent Tethys Ocean to the southeast and the widening proto-Atlantic to the west that fuelled intense evaporation and atmospheric humidity (Supplementary Fig. 1A). These vapor-laden air masses would have been transported by strengthened westerly trade winds or seasonal monsoonal flows.

6.2. Global impacts and palaeoenvironmental repercussions

The newly discovered Barrika glaciation contains evidence for the presence of glacial ice at a relatively low latitude during the Early Campanian, strongly corroborating the isotopic inferences of cooler temperatures pointed out by other researchers. Thus,

Fig. 17. Global evidence of the Barrika glaciation. The Campanian Barrika glaciation (82.8–80.96 Ma), that reached 35°N of palaeolatitude, correlates with a spike on hydration of Butcher Ridge Igneous Complex (BRIC) glasses by polar glacial ice and meltwater during the Late Cretaceous in Antarctica [⁴⁰Ar/³⁹Ar geochronology data for vitrophyre pod samples (green bars; but looking darker when matching glacial IRD and glacial deposits) (Nelson et al., 2022)] and with independent indicators (Salles et al., 2023) of global glaciation including: an increase in (i) average erosional rate, (ii) total erosion flux and (iii) net sediment flux to the ocean, and with a global decrease in (iv) total area covered by sediment, (v) endorheic basin area, and (vi) Ordinary least squares regression curve (OLS) [from the multivariate regression analysis carried out on normalized cumulative area covered by sediments (SCOV) and physiographic variety (PVAR)] (Salles et al., 2023). Palaeolatitudinal reach of ice-rafted debris and glaciogenic deposits from different authors (see references listed in the caption of Fig. 1); palaeolatitudes based on Lawver et al. (2014). PhanDA global mean surface temperature showing grey shading that correspond to different confident levels and the pinkie red line that shows the average solution (Judd et al., 2024). Global climate states from (Judd et al., 2024).

palaeoceanographic data from the Blake Nose (ODP1050 and ODP1049) indicate a marked positive shift in benthic $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ starting around 83 Ma (Huber et al., 2002), coinciding with the inception of the Barrika glaciation (82.8 Ma). This positive shift and the resulting temperature decrease mark the onset of the cool period that persisted through the late Campanian and Maastrichtian (Huber et al., 2002). Following the peak warmth of the Cretaceous hot greenhouse (~97–91 Ma), this long-lasting cooling trend developed between 91 and 78 Ma, recorded in a global compilation of benthic foraminiferal isotope data from multiple ocean basins by a significant increase in benthic $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and an associated decrease in $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (Friedrich et al., 2012).

A suite of geological signatures worldwide suggests a global impact of the Campanian Barrika glaciation (82.6–80.96 Ma) as this period exhibits evidence of widespread erosion, hinting at a potential link to sea-level fluctuations. The concentration of coeval N-S and NW-SE striking erosional surfaces at various palaeolatitudes in the Northern Hemisphere (36°, 42°, and 50° Surlyk et al., 2008; Gale et al., 2013, 2021) points towards a globally synchronous process capable of driving significant erosion, potentially analogous to the subaerial exposure during Pleistocene lowstands. The deep erosional Waco Channel in mid-Texas (70 km wide, >200 m deep, spanning the mid-Texas Hiatus, 83.4–81.5 Ma) is temporally synchronous with the Barrika glaciation (Gale et al., 2021). While the precise magnitude of sea-level fall during the Barrika glaciation is still debated, the presence of such a significant erosional feature strongly suggests a considerable base-level drop, mirroring the impact of eustatic changes during more recent glacial cycles. Evidence of erosion during the Barrika glaciation was also coupled with condensation of some sedimentary sequences. Some coupled examples include the condensed 16 m-thick UC14 biozone in Europe (Wolfgring et al., 2018), an extremely condensed 1 m-thick UC14 biozone in the Pacific (Bralower et al., 2006) and a 12 m-thick section of the UC14a and UC14b subzones in the southeastern Indian Ocean (Russo, 2013). Collectively, all these widespread sedimentary anomalies which are temporally coeval with the glaciomarine record of the Barrika glaciation in Spain (82.8–80.96 Ma), suggests a global glaciation for this period (Fig. 17).

6.3. *Allogenic forcing, atmospheric CO₂, and climate system dynamics*

While the precise trigger for the Barrika glaciation remains elusive, a study by Macdonald et al. (2019) highlights the significant role of large-scale tectonic forces in shaping Earth's climate, potentially setting the stage for such glacial events. Such forces highlight a compelling link between arc-continent collisions in the tropics and Earth's climate state over multi-million-year timescales. Notably, peaks in tropical suture lengths generally correlate with the latitudinal distribution of glaciogenic deposits (Macdonald et al., 2019). Interestingly, during the Campanian, around 82–81 Ma, (Macdonald et al., 2019) identified a substantial increase in suture zones that uniquely did not align with the typical latitudinal record of glacial deposits as occurred in other well-known global glaciations (see Fig. 2 of ref. Macdonald et al., 2019). This peak in tropical sutures, however, coincides with the unusually low-latitude Barrika glaciation, which extended down to 35°N, offering partial support for their broader conclusions about the influence of tropical tectonics on global climate.

In addition to the geochemical evidence of cooling during the early Cretaceous, and the widespread physical evidence of erosion and condensation, additional global evidence supports the global nature of the Barrika glaciation. The time period coincided with (i) a peak of ultra-depleted δD meltwater signals from Antarctic ice sheets (Nelson et al., 2022); note the strong match between a maximum of Cretaceous meltwater-related vitrophyre glass, (vertical green bar) (83–81 Ma) and the time span of the Barrika glaciation 82.8–80.96 Ma, (dark blue histogram bar) (Fig. 17) and (ii) global independent modelled palaeoclimate indicators (Salles et al., 2023) coupling with increases in average erosional rate, total erosion fluxes, and net sediment fluxes to

the ocean (Salles et al., 2023) all of them compatible with a global glaciation (Fig. 17).

Palaeoclimate models support the concept that CO₂ is the dominant control on Phanerozoic climate and marked the Late Cretaceous as the climate optimum of the Mesozoic (Judd et al., 2024). The Barrika glaciation, the lowest latitudinal glaciation in the Phanerozoic since the Last Palaeozoic Ice Age (LPIA) (Jurikova et al., 2025), occurred when Mesozoic temperatures have been modelled near their highest (Judd et al., 2024) (Fig. 17). The Barrika glaciation coincided with atmospheric $p\text{CO}_2$ estimates of 700–800 ppmv (Judd et al., 2024) (Fig. 17), double the mean reconstructed low $p\text{CO}_2$ of about 330 ± 210 ppm during much of the LPIA (Jurikova et al., 2025), when ice sheets reached 30°N (Rosa and Isbell, 2021), compared to 35°N in the Barrika glaciation. The occurrence of a 1.84 Myr glaciation in the Cretaceous super-greenhouse with ice caps grounding at 35°N palaeolatitude happened regardless of the elevated modelled $p\text{CO}_2$ values for the Cretaceous (Judd et al., 2024), demonstrating estimates of palaeo- $p\text{CO}_2$ are still questionable and/or global surface palaeotemperature estimates are problematic (Barclay and Wing, 2016). Existing palaeo- $p\text{CO}_2$ proxies for the Campanian (83.65–72.17 Ma) (Gale et al., 2020), including determinations from Ginkgo stomatal indexes (~550–590 ppm) (Quan et al., 2009) and palaeosol carbonates (550–502 ppm, average 520 ppm) (Orr et al., 2022), lack detailed geochronological controls. Moreover, estimates of palaeo- $p\text{CO}_2$ higher than 430 ppm from stomatal indexes should be regarded with caution (Barclay and Wing, 2016).

The identification of extensive glaciogenic deposits at an unexpectedly low palaeolatitude of 35°N during the Late Cretaceous provides compelling direct evidence for transient ice cap development, challenging the prevailing view of a consistently warm Cretaceous period. The substantial scale of the associated palaeomassif, exceeding that of contemporary sub-Antarctic glaciers, coupled with synchronous global sedimentary hiatuses and erosional features, suggests a far-reaching cryospheric influence on oceanographic processes and continental margin evolution. While the precise interplay of tectonic forcing and atmospheric CO₂ levels in triggering this mid-latitude glaciation warrants further investigation, the subtropical glaciers of the Barrika event underscores the dynamic nature of Earth climate system and the potential for significant ice caps growth at low latitudes even during generally warm intervals.

6.4. *The Cretaceous Barrika IRD Record Duration: Cenozoic Comparisons*

The duration, intensity, and internal variability of the Barrika glaciation are comparable to other Cenozoic and Pleistocene glaciations in terms of complexity (Gibbard and Hughes, 2021). The glaciomarine record in Barrika has been documented within the nanofossil biozone UC14 (Fig. 3, Supplementary Table 2); the first occurrence of ice-rafted dropstones (IRDp) is at the base of this biozone (UC14) at 82.8 Ma (Gale et al., 2020). These dropstones are found in laminated marlstones directly below the sedimentary record of glaciomarine unit 1. The last glaciomarine facies were recorded at the top of glaciomarine unit 5, just below the upper limit of the UC14 biozone, at 80.96 Ma (Gale et al., 2020). Overall, this interval of time means evidence of glaciation with active calving fronts and associated drifting icebergs recorded within a span of 1.84 Myr, which is also consistent with the widespread presence of cold-water and high-latitude taxa throughout this entire interval (Fig. 3 and 5). This evidence indicates that tidewater glaciers were continuously present and active, though they underwent different evolutionary stages and periods of intensification. In comparison, the Quaternary is known for its stratigraphical complexities (Gibbard and Hughes, 2021), and this complexity is also expected in ancient cryospheres. Glacial stratigraphic records are inherently complex because terrestrial successions are often discontinuous, erosional, and highly variable, rarely preserving a complete sequence of events (Gibbard and Hughes, 2021). Based on current data, the Barrika glaciation is

estimated to have lasted 1.84 Myr. During this time, at least five major glacial events were recorded (Fig. 2D), corresponding to glaciomarine units 1-5 (Fig. 3). Specifically, there was one event during subzone UC14a, two during UC14b, and two during UC14c/d (Figs. 2D and 3). During glacial maxima, glaciers advanced and formed grounding lines

on the shelf. Conversely, during glacial minima, glacial retreats occurred, with the calving front moving back toward Iberia. However, even during these retreats, drifting icebergs continued to release IRD, IRDb, and IRDp, indicating that tidewater glaciers had active calving fronts even during retreating stages (Figs. 2 and 3).

Fig. 18. Mismatch between multiproxy global evidence of an active Cretaceous cryosphere and modelled palaeotemperatures and estimate climate stages for the Cretaceous. (A) PhanDA global mean surface temperature showing grey shading that correspond to different confident levels and the pinkie red line that shows the average solution (Judd et al., 2024). Global climate states from (Judd et al., 2024). (B) Spikes on hydration of Butcher Ridge Igneous Complex (BRIC) glasses by polar glacial ice and meltwater during the Late Cretaceous in Antarctica, with ages based on $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ geochronology data for vitrophyre pod samples (Nelson et al., 2022). (C) Palaeolatitudinal reach of ice-rafted debris and glaciogenic deposits from different authors (see references listed in the caption of Fig. 1); palaeolatitudes based on Lawver et al. (2014). The Barrika glaciation is indicated. Lowermost latitudinal Cretaceous IRD from (Rodríguez-López et al., 2016). (D) Temporal distribution of active plateau and high-altitude Cretaceous cryospheres: (1) Berriasian–Hauterivian high-altitude glacial debris flow deposits (Ordos Basin, China) (Cheng et al., 2002); (2) Hauterivian plateau permafrost (Ordos Basin, China) (Rodríguez-López et al., 2022); (3) Barremian ice sheet-related meltwater isotopic signals in Cretaceous hydrothermal zircons (Yang et al., 2013) (see Wu et al., 2022); (4) Cenomanian–Turonian IRD in plateaus desert systems, South China Block (Wu and Rodríguez-López, 2021) and (5) IRD in the Songliao Basin (Wang et al., 1996) (see Wu et al., 2022). (E) Temporal distribution of Jurassic and Cretaceous glendonites (Rogov et al., 2023). (F) Likelihood of glacio-eustatic influence and typical maximum short-term sea-level change in meters (Ray et al., 2019). (G) Geological time and Cretaceous stages time limits from Gale et al. (2020).

The Barrika glaciation shows similarities with the initiation and evolution of the Cordilleran Ice Sheet (CIS) in North America and its record in the Gulf of Alaska during the late Pliocene and early Pleistocene (e.g., Prueher and Rea, 2001; Sánchez-Montes et al., 2020). The initiation and evolution of the CIS during the Late Pliocene are documented through deep-sea sediment records in the Gulf of Alaska (GOA). However, the maximum time recorded by IRD and first records of active calving glaciers varies among deep sea drilling cores at different locations.

Chronological markers for tidewater glaciation onset vary slightly between sites: Ice-Rafted Debris (IRD) is first seen at Site 887 at 3.9 Ma (Prueher and Rea, 2001), although mass accumulation rates (MAR) for IRD were very small prior to 2.6 Ma (Sánchez-Montes et al., 2020), whereas the first significant IRD peak at Site U1417, marking the onset of tidewater glacier presence in southwest Alaska, occurs at 2.9 Ma (Sánchez-Montes et al., 2020). This initial expansion was followed by a major intensification phase, correlating with the intensification of Northern Hemisphere Glaciation (iNHG) (Sánchez-Montes et al., 2020), characterized by a rapid IRD increase at Site 887 around 2.75 Ma (Prueher and Rea, 2001), and spanning 2.7 to 2.4 Ma at Site U1417 (Sánchez-Montes et al., 2020). During this intensified phase, site U1417 reveals diamict layers alternating with bioturbated muds (Sánchez-Montes et al., 2020), indicating that the CIS maintained a stable glacial tidewater margin consistently discharging icebergs into the GOA (Sánchez-Montes et al., 2020). The Barrika glaciation glaciomarine record is more proximal than these recent analogue records but still shows similarities; as in the GOA, during the Campanian intensification of glaciation associated with glaciomarine diamictites have been recorded, amid a continuous release of IRD, IRDb and IRDp from drifting icebergs (Fig. 3).

Regarding the maximum time recorded with IRD in the GOA sites, the record of IRD activity utilized from offshore ODP Site 887 spans the interval from 3.2 to 1.9 Myr. This time span provides a detailed record of IRD presence over a duration of 1.3 Myr. Although the earliest suggested glacial influence in the GOA, based on IRD at Site 887, has been reported to date back to 5.5 Ma (Prueher and Rea, 2001). The core record at IODP Site U1417, which documents the glaciomarine history of the CIS, spans 2.9 Ma to 1.7 Ma. This specific interval documents a 1.2-Myr glaciomarine history.

Similarly, the Cretaceous Barrika glaciation record spans 82.8 Ma to 80.96 Ma, representing a 1.84-Myr glaciomarine succession (Figs. 2D and 3). The initial evidence of active tidewater glacier calving is recorded at 82.8 Ma by the presence of ice-rafted dropstones and biodebris at the base of nannofossil subzone UC14a (Fig. 3). The record comprises five distinct glaciomarine units (Figs. 2D and 3), including undermelt and rainout diamictites associated with ice shelves, and subglacial diamictites indicative of grounding lines. The expansion of the Cretaceous Iberian Ice Cap is evidenced by corresponding peaks in IRD, IRDb, and IRDp (ice-rafted debris) delivery.

The chronostratigraphic records of both the Cordilleran and Barrika glaciations demonstrate remarkably analogous patterns of evolution (e.g. Sánchez-Montes et al., 2020; Prueher and Rea, 2001). Both records are characterized by protracted periods of waxing and waning ice sheets/ice caps, as evidenced by fluctuations in IRD proxies over their respective durations (1.2/1.3 Myr vs 1.84 Myr). The Barrika record reveals that IRD, IRDb, and IRDp were continuously deposited on the ocean floor, even during glacial minima. Furthermore, the delivery of IRD, IRDb and IRDp increased prior to glacial maxima and decreased following them (Fig. 3), suggesting a direct and sensitive link between iceberg discharge and the state of the ice cap. The glaciomarine records of the CIS and the Campanian Barrika glaciations, despite their disparate temporal settings, reflect fundamental and recurrent mechanisms of ice-sheet/ice-cap growth, decay, and marine-based interaction.

The sedimentary record of IRD in the Barrika glaciation spanning 1.84 Myr is consistent with other Cenozoic analogues including the record of IRD in sites 982 and 985, in the northern North Atlantic and

Norwegian-Greenland Sea, which IRD records spans of 2.8 and 3 Myrs respectively (Baumann and Huber, 1999), as well as in sites 644 and 642, where the sedimentary record of IRD spans 3.5 Myr (Jansen et al., 2000). In this regard, the Barrika glaciation behaved similar to major Cenozoic glaciations in the Northern Hemisphere.

6.5. Multiproxy evidence of Cretaceous cryosphere

Previous reviews on the latitudinal extent of ice-rafted debris and glacial deposits in the Phanerozoic have not considered the full climate variability of the Mesozoic (Fig. 1). We review published information of multiproxy evidence of an active Cretaceous cryosphere (Fig. 18). The Cretaceous has a duration of 77.06 Myr (Gale et al., 2020). Of this duration we note that (i) during 42.4 Myr (55% of Cretaceous time) Antarctica recorded evidence of meltwater associated with ice-sheets (Fig. 18B) (Nelson et al., 2022); (ii) during 68.2 Myr (53% of Cretaceous time) the Cretaceous had ice-rafted debris and glacial deposits (Figs. 1C and 18C) (Frakes and Francis, 1988; Macquaker and Keller, 2005; Keller and Macquaker, 2015; Rodríguez-López et al., 2016, 2024; Alley et al., 2020; Schneider et al., 2020; Song et al., 2021; Jeans and Platten, 2021; Gao et al., 2024); (iii) during 31.3 Myr (24% of Cretaceous time) glendonites have been found (Fig. 18E) (Rogov et al., 2021; Rogov et al., 2023); and (iv) during 66.4 Myr (86% of Cretaceous time) glacio-eustasy was the driver of significant short-term sea-level changes (Fig. 18F) (Ray et al., 2019). There is also evidence of active early Cretaceous permafrost in plateaus and high-altitude deserts coupling with geochemical palaeoclimate proxies (Rodríguez-López et al., 2022), IRD, glendonites and glacio-eustatic signals (Fig. 18C–18F).

The Barrika glaciation constitutes the lowest latitudinal evidence of grounded lines of tidewater glaciers since the Carboniferous (Figs. 1 and 18C), and the IRDp found in the late Aptian–early Albian of eastern Iberia constitute the lowest latitudinal IRD recorded in the Mesozoic (Figs. 1 and 18C; Supplementary Table 1). The mid-Aptian of Iberia exhibits evidence of frequent and pronounced sea-level oscillations, occurring at a rate of seven cycles per million years with amplitudes ranging from 8 to 127 m that have been linked to glacioeustasy (Peropadre et al., 2013). This evidence aligns with recent Aptian palaeoclimate models that support the presence of ice sheets in Antarctica (Nordt et al., 2024) and similar global evidence of Aptian glacio-eustasy (e.g. Horner et al., 2019; Ray et al., 2019).

The location of Iberia during the Cretaceous played a major role in the preservation of glacial and proglacial deposits, probably due to its key palaeogeographical location linked to ice-cap terminus (Rodríguez-López et al., 2024) during peak glaciations together with creation of accommodation space and an elevated Iberian Massif, as previously discussed.

There is still room for discovery and precision on the recurrence and paucity of Cretaceous glaciations, in particular for the Turonian and the Maastrichtian.

The occurrence of ice sheets about half the size of the modern Antarctic ice sheets during one of the warmest periods of the Phanerozoic eon, the Turonian (~91.2 Myr) has been detected (Bornemann et al., 2008). This is contrary to palaeoclimate proxies pointing to a monotonously hot Turonian greenhouse interval (MacLeod et al., 2013) but is backed up by recent data of ultra-depleted δD signals from Antarctica (Nelson et al., 2022) linked with long-lasting ice-sheet-related meltwater from 105 Ma to 72 Ma, peaking at c. 91.4 Ma (Nelson et al., 2022) as previously detected by (Bornemann et al., 2008). Despite this indirect geochemical evidence for the past existence of ice sheets obtained from the Atlantic Ocean and the Antarctic continent, identification of irrefutable and direct proof for global glaciation during the Turonian from the glaciomarine record remains elusive. For this time, glacio-eustatic oscillations are considered “equivocal” in the range of ~30 m by Ray et al. (2019) (Fig. 18F); it is interesting to note that a synchronous eustatic fall in mid-Turonian sea level have been detected (Jones et al., 2018). The potential for further discoveries of Turonian IRD and

glendonites in the geological record is significant.

The so-called “Cool Tropic Paradox” of the Late Campanian–Maastrichtian by which the absence of a major ice sheet during the Late Campanian–Maastrichtian, despite an interval of significant global cooling and superficial similarities to Eocene climate patterns, presents an intriguing challenge (Linnert et al., 2014). Linnert et al. (2014) asked in their paper: “Why, then, did significant continental ice-sheet growth occur at the E/O boundary, but not during the late Cretaceous, given the cooler Late Campanian and Maastrichtian water temperatures (surface and deep) and cooling at both high and subequatorial latitudes?” The answer is simple based on the information provided in Fig. 18: very probably because Late Campanian and Maastrichtian IRD and glacial deposits have not been yet discovered. However, absence of evidence is not evidence of absence. Glacial systems are powerful erosional agents, and long-term advances and retreats tend to erase sedimentological evidence; this together with a pre-Pangaea VS post-Pangaea scenarios could probably had a detrimental effect on the preservation bias of Mesozoic cryosphere evidence.

Advancing our understanding of Cretaceous climate dynamics necessitates improved geochronological frameworks for climate-sensitive systems. The Barrika glaciation, for instance, is precisely constrained by a detailed nannofossil biostratigraphy (Figs. 3–5), establishing a duration of 1.84 Myr. This stands in contrast to other Cretaceous glacial continental deposits, such as those in China, which often lack similarly precise age determinations, with reported ranges spanning Cenomanian to Turonian (Wu and Rodríguez-López, 2021).

Similarly, interpretations of warmer Cretaceous climates, particularly at high latitudes, would benefit from enhanced geochronological precision. For example, Klages et al. (2020) presented compelling evidence of a ‘temperate rainforest’ near the South Pole at a palaeolatitude of approximately 82°S during the Turonian–Santonian. Their study, published in *Nature* and entitled “*Temperate rainforests near the South Pole during peak Cretaceous warmth*,” described an intact 3-meter-long network of in situ fossil roots embedded in a mudstone matrix containing diverse pollen and spores. While this finding is significant, the reported age range for these deposits is Turonian–Santonian (~92–83 Ma), or Turonian–Early Campanian considering the updated geochronological scale of Gale et al. (2020). This substantial 9 Myr time span means that the reported root structures could have formed at any point within this protracted interval; considering that mean chronological ages of fine roots vary from <1 to 12 years in temperate, boreal and subarctic forests (Solly et al., 2018), these 3-m-long roots have encapsulated in the best case scenario a maximum of tens of years. If we stick to data, the record of rainforest in Antarctica confirms that plants developed roots during a decade at some point during a period lasting 9 million years.

In contrast, the Barrika glaciation is precisely dated to 82.8–80.96 Ma, with a duration of 1.84 Myr. Within this remarkably shorter period, five distinct glaciomarine units are recorded, indicating glacial advances and retreats with an apparent 360 kyr spacing (Fig. 3). The disparity in geochronological resolution between precisely dated low-latitude glacial events like the Barrika glaciation and broadly constrained high-latitude warmth proxies highlights a critical need: to fully comprehend the intricate dynamics of Cretaceous climate change, future research must prioritize robust, high-resolution geochronological constraints. By improving dating techniques, we can move beyond broad time intervals and begin to precisely decipher the synchronicity and causality of significant climatic shifts, such as glacial–interglacial cycles and periods of extreme polar warmth, thereby strengthening the scientific evidence and accuracy for Cretaceous climate reconstructions based on real physical data.

7. Conclusions

One of the best glaciomarine records preserved on Earth comes from the Late Cretaceous, when temperatures have been modelled near the

highest during the Mesozoic climate optimum. This exemplifies the need to reevaluate the validity of geochemical palaeoclimate proxies during the Cretaceous that ignore the evidence of an active cryosphere during this period of the Earth’s history. The Campanian Barrika glaciation (82.8–80.96 Ma) was characterized by tidewater glaciers grounded at an unusually low palaeolatitude (35°N). These tidewater glaciers had active calving zones delivering large icebergs to the palaeo-Atlantic Ocean. During the Barrika glaciation (1.84 Myr) a total of five glaciomarine units are recorded; however, the sedimentary record between these intervals, still contains ice-rafted debris, ice-rafted dropstones and ice-rafted biodebris, providing evidence of glacier retreated but still active tidewater glaciers in northern Iberia during glaciation minima. The multiproxy data approach developed in the analysis of the Barrika glaciation can help to recognize other unknown Mesozoic glacial records.

The traditional “Hothouse–Icehouse” dichotomy and the prevailing “Cretaceous greenhouse” narrative fail to accurately represent the geological record. A re-evaluation is imperative, given that the Cretaceous was characterized by the lowest latitudinal glaciation since the Last Paleozoic Ice Age (LPIA). During this period, meltwater presence linked to Antarctic ice sheets endured for 55% of its duration, with ice-rafted debris and glacial deposits present in 53% of the period, with glendonites found in 24% of Cretaceous time and the significant role of glacio-eustasy in short-term sea-level changes, affecting a remarkable 86% of the period. Collectively, this evidence fundamentally challenges the notion of an archetypal, ice-free Cretaceous world.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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